

ExtremeXP

Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for
Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions

**D7.2: Communication & dissemination, and
standardization activities**

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BiDS	Big Data from Space
CAIN	Conference on AI Engineering
CS	CS GROUP
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EC	European Commission
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
ECSA	European Conference on Software Architecture
EDBT	Extending Database Technology
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICTAI	International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence
IGARSS	International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
LPS	Living Planet Symposium
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV-SDN	Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
OSS	Open-Source Software
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
R&D	Research and Development
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package
X	Social media platform formerly known as Twitter

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D7.2) presents a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, and standardisation activities carried out throughout the ExtremeXP project. It consolidates the project's strategic approach, implemented actions, monitoring mechanisms, and achieved impact over the full project duration.

ExtremeXP's communication and dissemination strategy was designed to maximise the visibility, understanding, and uptake of the project's scientific and technical results across a wide range of stakeholders, including research communities, industry actors, public authorities, and European data and AI ecosystems. The strategy relied on a coherent brand identity, a central project website, active social media channels, scientific publications, participation in major European and international events, and structured collaboration within relevant clusters and initiatives.

Over the project lifetime, ExtremeXP achieved strong results in scientific dissemination, significantly exceeding initial targets in terms of publications and conference participation. The consortium contributed to a large number of peer reviewed articles, conference papers, and workshops, ensuring high visibility within academic and expert communities. Active participation in flagship European events (e.g. EDBT, VLDB, EBDVF, Big Data from Space, Living Planet Symposium) and clustering initiatives (EUDATA+, AI.BIG, Data Spaces Support Centre) further strengthened the project's positioning within the European data and AI landscape.

Communication activities ensured consistency and recognisability through well-defined visual identity guidelines and a wide range of communication materials, including templates, brochures, posters, newsletters, videos, and online content. The project website served as a central access point for project information, publications, deliverables, software, and news, supported by regular monitoring of digital performance indicators.

Standardisation activities were addressed from an alignment and monitoring perspective. While ExtremeXP did not aim to develop new standards, the project ensured consistency with relevant European and international initiatives through engagement with BDVA task forces, clustering activities, and domain specific communities. Use cases provided valuable feedback on the applicability of existing frameworks in real-world, data intensive and AI driven contexts.

Overall, ExtremeXP delivered a strong and coherent dissemination and communication effort, with particularly high impact in scientific and European collaborative domains. Despite some limitations in late-stage industrial outreach and largescale demonstrations, the project established solid foundations for long-term visibility, reuse, and sustainability of its results beyond the end of Horizon Europe funding.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable presents the Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan of the ExtremeXP project. Its main purpose is to define a structured and coherent framework to guide all communication and dissemination activities throughout the project's lifetime.

The document aims to ensure consistent messaging, strong visibility, and effective engagement with key stakeholders, including the scientific community, industry actors, policy makers and other relevant audiences. It supports the promotion of the project's objectives, activities and results, while fostering awareness, understanding and adoption of ExtremeXP outcomes.

The scope of this deliverable covers the overall communication and dissemination strategy, including objectives, target audiences, key messages, communication channels, tools, planned actions and monitoring indicators. It serves as a reference document for all project partners involved in communication-related activities.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is organised to provide a comprehensive and coherent overview of the communication and dissemination approach of the ExtremeXP project.

It first presents the overall communication and dissemination strategy, offering a clear synthesis of the project's objectives, target audiences, key messages and positioning. The document then details the ExtremeXP brand identity, including its visual elements and communication materials, in order to ensure consistency and recognisability across all project outputs.

The deliverable further describes the main communication channels used to promote the project, with particular attention to the project website and social media platforms, which serve as key tools for visibility, engagement and information sharing. It also outlines the methods used to monitor communication performance through website and channel analytics.

Finally, the document details the dissemination and communication activities implemented throughout the project. These include scientific publications, participation in conferences and events, digital communication actions, and liaison activities with other relevant EU-funded initiatives and clusters. The deliverable also addresses standardisation aspects from an alignment and monitoring perspective, presents the monitoring framework and evaluation of dissemination and communication KPIs, and documents the responses to reviewers' recommendations. Together, these elements provide a comprehensive view of the project's dissemination outcomes, impact, and long-term sustainability.

2 Strategic Communication and dissemination Plan at a Glance

The communication and dissemination strategy of the ExtremeXP project is designed to maximise the visibility, impact and uptake of its results by addressing a diverse range of stakeholders through appropriate messages and channels.

The strategy pursues the following main objectives:

- To increase awareness and understanding of the ExtremeXP project and its innovative approach to data analytics.
- To promote the project's results, tools and methodologies to relevant stakeholders.
- To support engagement, knowledge exchange and collaboration across scientific, industrial and institutional communities.
- To contribute to the long-term exploitation and sustainability of project outcomes.

The primary target audiences include:

- Research and scientific communities

- Industry stakeholders and technology providers
- Policy makers and public institutions
- Innovation ecosystems and data-driven organisations
- A wider audience with interest in artificial intelligence and data analytics

Key communication and dissemination channels include the project website, social media platforms, scientific publications, events and conferences, workshops, newsletters and promotional materials. All activities are aligned with the project's visual identity and core messages to ensure coherence, recognisability and impact.

3 Brand Identity and Project Materials

3.1 Project Identity

The ExtremeXP logo has been designed to convey several of the project's key values: advanced technology, innovation, people at the heart of the process, and the integration of artificial intelligence.

Figure 3-1: Project Logo

Logo Design

The ExtremeXP logo is designed around several key symbols that represent the essence of the project:

The Human at the Centre: The central element of the logo is a stylised humanoid figure. This symbol represents the process aspect of the project, highlighting the centrality of the individual in experimentation and analysis. It emphasises that the human being is at the heart of the processes, and that the aim is to make the experience more accessible and understandable, while at the same time being guided by technology.

The Target: The entity surrounding man refers to the experimental approach. It symbolises a well-defined framework, with a target for each objective or mission. This circle also represents the circularity of processes and the optimisation of results.

The Small Electrons: The small particles escaping from the target are a reference to artificial intelligence. These electrons are a symbol of advanced technology and the way AI is fluidly and dynamically integrated into the overall process, creating a link with research and innovation.

White and midnight blue versions: The logo can also be presented in midnight blue and white. This variation ensures excellent legibility and visual consistency when used on media where colour is not possible or desirable, for example in black and white prints.

Rectangular logo: Used mainly for horizontal formats, where the 'ExtremeXP' text is located to the right of the icon. This makes it quick and easy to read while maintaining the visual balance of the logo.

Square logo: For more compact formats where a smaller logo is required (for example, profiles on social networks), the square version is preferred. Here, the icon is more prominent, while the 'ExtremeXP' text can be omitted, reduced or even removed for a better fit.

Figure 3-2: Project colour palette

Colour details: ExtremeXP's colour palette is made up of several cool, modern and dynamic shades.

#0E1021 (Midnight Blue)

A deep, elegant blue that symbolises technology, confidence and reliability. Often used on dark backgrounds or to add depth to a visual presentation. It also denotes a certain solidity.

#3766AF (Light Blue)

A lighter shade of blue, associated with notions of professionalism, reliability and advanced technology. It is a basic colour for the logo and other important visual elements.

#6BBC8C (Light Green)

Light green represents innovation, growth, and a certain sustainable aspect.

#2E303A (Dark Grey)

This dark grey gives a professional, understated look, and helps the brighter colours of the logo or other elements stand out.

#5086C6 (Medium Blue)

A softer blue that blends well with other shades. It evokes stability and support.

#7AC296 (Soft Green)

A lighter, soothing green, symbolising harmony and creativity.

#FFFFFF (White)

White is used to create sharp contrasts and bring clarity. It maintains a minimalist and modern design, emphasising other visual elements.

#82C0EA (Light Blue)

A pastel blue that completes the range of blues in the palette. This blue adds lightness and freshness, with a touch of dynamism.

#C8E2C8 (Very Light Green)

A very light green that evokes a sense of lightness and freshness. It is used as an accent and adds a touch of softness to the whole palette.

All Round Gothic Bold

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N	A B C D E F G H I J K L M N
O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z À Á	O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z À Á
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q	a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q
r s t u v w x y z à á é î ð ø ü	r s t u v w x y z à á é î ð ø ü
& 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 (\$ £ € . , ! ?)	& 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 (\$ £ € . , ! ?)

Figure 3-3: Project Font

Font: The font chosen for ExtremeXP is All Round Gothic Bold. It is a bold, geometric sans-serif font. The sans-serif font is chosen for its legibility and modern look. It is easy to read, even in small formats. It also gives a clear, uncluttered look. The choice of 'bold' style gives strength to the message. It symbolises solidity and stability while providing visibility. It makes the text impactful and easily identifiable, which is essential for ExtremeXP's visual identity.

3.2 Project Templates

These templates were designed to structure and harmonize ExtremeXP project presentations, highlighting objectives, progress, and results, while ensuring visual consistency suitable for interim reviews and consortium partners.

Word

Figure 3-4: Project deliverable template

PowerPoint

The PowerPoint template serves as a common framework for all ExtremeXP project presentations, particularly during Interim Project Reviews. It meets several needs.

Figure 3-5: Project power point presentation – main page

Visual and institutional consistency

- The design incorporates the project's graphic elements (logo, colours, backgrounds, typography).
- The mandatory information is included (Horizon Europe funding, agreement numbers, project slogan: Experiment driven and user eXperience-oriented Analytics for eXtremely Precise outcomes and decisions).

Figure 3-6: Project power point presentation – overview page

Clarity and readability

- Each section is defined: WP Overview, Tasks, Timeline & Deliverables, Achievements, KPIs.
- Organization by tasks (T4.1, T4.2, etc.) illustrates objectives, progress made, key results, and next steps.

Figure 3-7: Project power point presentation – Timeline & Deliverables & Milestones page

Highlighting results

- Specific slides (e.g., Summary of Achievements, KPIs) highlight innovations, prototypes, and methods developed.
- Monitoring is structured to show the impact on use cases.

Figure 3-8: Project power point presentation – Specific slides page

Figure 3-9: Project power point presentation – final page

Practical utility

- The template provides a framework that can be adapted to each Work Package (WP), ensuring consistency in presentations made to European reviewers.
- It saves time by following a clear logic, rather than recreating a presentation each time.

3.3 Project Brochure

This 3-fold flyer gives a concise, structured presentation of the key aspects of ExtremeXP, highlighting its methodology, the technologies used, the use cases and contact information.

Page 1 (Front of flyer)

Main title: 'ExtremeXP offers an innovative approach called 'Experiment-driven analysis', placing the user at the heart of the analytical process.'

The quote explains ExtremeXP's methodology, which is user-centric and based on experiment-driven analysis. It also highlights the interactive and explainable aspect of the project, with the aim of improving the reliability of results through interactive visual techniques.

Main image

The image of the ExtremeXP logo and graphic elements in the background is used to attract the eye while visually presenting the values of the project: technology, interactivity and innovation.

Figure 3-10: Project Brochure - page 1

Page 2 (Inside the flyer - Use cases)

This page is dedicated to use cases in various sectors. It describes concrete applications of ExtremeXP in key areas:

Crisis Management: Modelling flash floods in the city of Nîmes, using AI to improve forecasts compared with a reference hydrodynamic model. This case shows the importance of AI in natural crisis management.

Cybersecurity: Improving the detection of cyber-attacks by linking alerts to attacker behaviour, thereby improving the detection of attacks in real time while reducing false positives.

Public Safety: Using ExtremeXP's capabilities to improve public safety by detecting urban fires and making real-time decisions using AI and augmented reality (AR).

Mobility: Optimising transport policies tailored to the specific needs of authorities, focusing on low-emission zones and autonomous vehicles. The use of AI and augmented reality enables interactive visualisation of results.

Manufacturing: Maximising the uptime of industrial machinery by enabling technical departments to make informed decisions about potential failures of critical components, reducing false alarms and improving predictive maintenance.

Figure 3-11: Project Brochure – page 2

Page 3-4-5 (Inside the flyer - The project)

Project summary: ‘ExtremeXP adopts a modular approach, centered around an experiment engine, integrating modelling, planning, enhancement of experiment descriptions, execution of complex analytical workflows, and monitoring.’

Figure 3-12: Project Brochure – inside the flyer

The project adopts a modular approach centred around an experiment engine. This allows it to be easily integrated into various application domains, based on planning, execution of complex analytical workflows, and performance monitoring.

Overview of ExtremeXP: The diagram shows the interaction between the various technologies and methodologies involved in the project:

- Transparent & Interactive Decision Making: Interactive and transparent decisions.
- User-driven AutoML: Optimisation of AI models guided by the user.
- Experimentation Engine: The engine that generates experiments and executes workflows.
- Extreme Data & Knowledge Management: Secure, distributed management of data and knowledge.
- Analysis-aware Data Integration: Integration of data with particular attention to its quality and origin.

This diagram illustrates the integration of these technologies, highlighting the synergies between them.

The Consortium: This section presents the partners involved in the project, with logos of prestigious companies and institutions. This shows the international scope of the project and the network of expertise it mobilises.

Page 4 (Last page - Contact)

Contact details: This page contains contact information for the coordinators, the technical manager, the innovation manager and the communications contact.

There is also a QR code for quick access to more information online.

Mention of funding

The European Union is mentioned through the Horizon programme, underlining the institutional support for the project.

Figure 3-13: Project Brochure – Final page

3.4 Project Poster

The ExtremeXP poster gives an overview of the project, its objectives and the innovative technologies it encompasses.

Figure 3-14: Project Poster

Main Title: ‘Experiment Driven and User Experience Oriented Analytics for Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions’. This title highlights the dual approach of the project: experimentation and user experience. It reflects ExtremeXP’s main objective, which is to deliver extremely precise outcomes and decisions through the use of experiment-driven and user-centred analytics.

Co-financing: ‘The ExtremeXP project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Program HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-01, under Grant Agreement No. 101093164’. This co-financing can be seen on all documents, along with the European Union flag. The project is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon programme, which highlights the scale and institutional support enjoyed by ExtremeXP.

Key components of the project:

- a. **User Driven AutoML:** This section presents ExtremeXP’s innovative research into Machine Learning (ML). It includes concepts such as:
 - **Simulation-based data augmentation:** Augmenting data by simulation to improve model performance.
 - **Constraint-aware algorithms:** Algorithms that take into account specific constraints during learning.
 - **User-preference model selection:** Machine learning model selection based on user preferences.
 - **Continual learning:** This allows models to adapt and learn from new data without losing previous knowledge.
 - **Optimal ML pipeline deployment:** Optimal deployment of ML pipelines in a variety of environments.

- b. **Experimentation Engine:** This engine is an essential component for modelling experiments, enriching descriptions with context, managing the planning of analysis workflows, and monitoring execution using system and user metrics.
- c. **Analysis-aware Data Integration:** This section deals with the challenges associated with data processing, including, automatic data set selection and management of data quality issues such as missing, incomplete, incorrect or duplicate data in user-driven workflows.
- d. **Extreme Data & Knowledge Management:** This section deals with the secure and distributed management of data and knowledge throughout their lifecycle. This covers the creation and sharing of analytical resources, while guaranteeing their security and effectiveness in the analysis process.
- e. **Transparent & Interactive Decision Making:** The emphasis is on improving user confidence through interactive explanations of the decisions made by ML models and analyses. This transparency is achieved through interactive visuals and the use of augmented reality (AR), allowing users to actively engage with the experimentation engine.
- f. **User-driven Optimization of Complex Analytics:** This part captures user intentions and feedback via gamification, and aligns them with backend analytics to create personalised user profiles. The aim is to improve the ExtremeXP experience for each user, by adapting the tools to their specific needs.

Use Cases: This section illustrates the application areas of ExtremeXP:

- **Public Safety:** Using situational intelligence for decision-making in public protection and disaster relief (PPDR) situations.
- **Cybersecurity:** Increasing situational awareness in cybersecurity, enabling more effective management of threats.
- **Manufacturing:** Preventing failures in the manufacturing industry using advanced analysis tools.
- **Mobility:** Flexible analysis and visualisation of data relating to mobility and transport systems.
- **Crisis Management:** Tools to improve crisis management, particularly in situations where rapid reaction is essential.

3.5 Project Banner

Here's the evolution of our ExtremeXP banner. Over the past year, we've refined our visual identity to better reflect our growth and innovation in the field of experiment-driven analytics and AI. From a minimalist design to a more dynamic and sophisticated look, our updated banner represents the continued progress of ExtremeXP as we move forward with cutting-edge solutions for our users.

First ExtremeXP Banner

Figure 3-15: First ExtremeXP Banner

Dominant Colours: The first banner stands out with blue and green tones. Blue dominates, symbolizing technology, trust, and innovation, while green adds a sense of freshness, growth, and sustainability. These colours are used in a gradient, creating a soothing and modern atmosphere.

Visual Design:

- Circuitry and geometric shapes in the banner represent artificial intelligence, connectivity, and technological innovation.
- The abstract lines and connection points symbolize a data network or an interconnected system, highlighting the technological and experimental nature of the ExtremeXP project.
- The use of modern, clean typography in the ExtremeXP logo enhances the idea of a company at the cutting edge of technology.

Overall Mood: This banner has a futuristic and minimalistic style, remaining simple but very effective in conveying a sense of advanced technology. The graphic elements reminiscent of circuit boards and networks symbolize ExtremeXP's technologies, focused on experimentation and optimizing results.

Second ExtremeXP Banner (One year later)

Figure 3-16: Second ExtremeXP Banner

Dominant Colours: The second banner presents a similar gradient of green and blue, but this time with a smoother and clearer transition between the two hues. This creates a sense of continuity and fluidity, suggesting the project's evolution over time.

Visual Design:

- The circuitry is still present but with softer, sharper shapes. The network pattern is even more developed, with geometric forms and fluid lines intersecting, creating a sense of smooth connection and interaction between different entities.
- The textured background is slightly more complex, introducing diagonal shapes and dot patterns that bring depth and movement to the image. This design choice makes the banner more dynamic and visually interesting.

Overall Mood: This banner retains the futuristic and modern style but seems a bit more mature and evolved compared to the first one. The more complex texture and new graphic elements reinforce the idea of a project that has matured and continues to develop. The inclusion of point and line patterns suggests more interaction and complexity in ExtremeXP's technological ecosystem.

3.6 Project Rollup

This roll-up presents a visual overview of the ExtremeXP project, highlighting the different stages of the analysis process, the key technologies used and the use cases where ExtremeXP can have a significant impact.

Figure 3-17: Project Rollup

Visual analysis process: The roll-up clearly illustrates ExtremeXP's analysis process across three interconnected spaces: Experimentation Engine, User Experience Space, and Knowledge Space. Here is a summary of the key stages:

a. Experimentation Engine

- **Creating the experiment:** First stage where users or researchers create a new set of experiments.
- **Select experiment variants:** Here, different variants are selected to refine the experiment. This includes elements such as:
 - ML task (machine learning task)
 - Simulation
 - Visual analytics

This part of the process shows how experimentation is used to test various hypotheses and refine models.

b. User Experience Space

- **Intentions and Context:** The user defines their intention ('Predict average repair time', for example) and provides the context required for the analysis.
- **User Feedback:** A feedback loop is created, allowing the user to interact with the system and adjust their expectations or preferences according to the results obtained.

This component emphasises the importance of personalisation and user engagement in the analysis process.

c. Knowledge Space

- **Algorithm and model selection:** Algorithms and models are selected according to the data available, to ensure efficient and accurate analysis.
- **Knowledge management:** This section highlights the importance of organising and integrating knowledge into the analyses, to ensure reliable and relevant results.

These steps illustrate the integration of data, knowledge and models to provide decisions based on in-depth analysis.

Key technologies: The roll-up also highlights the key technologies supporting the project:

- Experimentation Engine
- Analysis-aware Data Integration
- User Driven AutoML
- Extreme Data and Knowledge Management
- Transparent and Interactive Decision Making
- User Driven Optimization of Complex Analytics

Each of these technologies represents an innovation in the field of data analysis, ranging from data integration to the optimisation of complex analyses, as well as improving the transparency of decisions made by models.

Use Cases: Use cases show how ExtremeXP can be applied in different fields. These practical applications demonstrate the flexibility and potential impact of the project:

- **Public Safety:** Situational intelligence for decision-making in public safety.
- **Cybersecurity:** Increasing situational awareness in cybersecurity.
- **Manufacturing:** Failure prevention in the manufacturing industry.
- **Crisis Management:** The use of ExtremeXP in crisis management.
- **Mobility:** Analysis tools to improve mobility and transport systems.

Each use case reflects the project's adaptability to different business sectors.

Partners and Co-Financing: The European Union logo and information on co-financing by the Horizon programme show the importance and institutional support of this project.

Project partners: The roll-up shows a list of partners involved in ExtremeXP, demonstrating the collaboration between several renowned institutions, companies and universities in the field of technology and innovation.

3.7 Project Newsletters

Newsletters represent an important communication channel for ExtremeXP, enabling regular and structured dissemination of project news, results, and activities to a broad range of stakeholders, including researchers, industrial actors, institutional stakeholders, and members of the European data and AI ecosystem.

At the early stages of the project, newsletter activities were coordinated by **Activeeon**, in line with the initial communication strategy. Following the departure of Activeeon from the consortium, the responsibility for newsletter production and dissemination was taken over by **Interactive 4D (I4D)**, ensuring continuity of communication activities without interruption to the overall dissemination objectives.

ExtremeXP newsletters are published via the project website and relayed through the project's communication channels, including social media. They provide concise and accessible content highlighting:

- project milestones and technical progress,
- key scientific publications and public deliverables,
- participation in conferences, workshops, and clustering events,
- collaboration activities with other EU-funded projects and clusters,
- announcements of upcoming events and dissemination actions.

During the project lifetime, newsletters were released to reflect the increasing maturity of ExtremeXP results and to maintain engagement with external audiences. They complemented other communication tools such as the project website, social media channels, and promotional materials, contributing to coherent and consistent messaging across all partners.

Overall, the newsletters supported the visibility of ExtremeXP, reinforced dissemination efforts at European and international levels, and ensured sustained communication with the project's stakeholder community throughout the project duration.

Newsletter 2024

- [January](#)
- [February](#)
- [March](#)
- [April](#)
- [May](#)
- [June](#)
- [July](#)
- [August & September](#)
- [EBDVF 2024](#)
- [October](#)
- [November](#)
- [December](#)

Newsletter 2025

- [January](#)
- [February](#)
- [June & July](#)
- [September](#)

Newsletter 2026

- [January](#)

Figure 3-18: Project newsletter overview

The newsletter content is as follows:

ExtremeXP
Experiment Driven and User Experience Oriented Analytics for Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions

Happy New Year 2026!
As we step into 2026, we would like to thank our community for its continued interest, engagement, and contributions to the ExtremeXP journey. A new year means new perspectives, new experiments, and new opportunities to advance human-centered, experimentation-driven analytics together.

Join our beta-tests
Build, run, and optimize analytics through **experiment-driven workflows** and **explainable AI**.

Register and test the Framework

By joining the beta-tests, you gain access to the **complete map of the ExtremeXP framework**, giving you the freedom to explore, test, and experiment **at your own pace** with one or several of its key components, based on your needs, use cases, and areas of interest.

What will you get?

- Transparent & traceable decisions
- Fast, user-driven experimentation
- A modular framework powered by the Experimentation Engine

Test it now without delay!

Explore the framework

”

Figure 3-19: Project Newsletter example

4 Project Website

4.1 Website Overview

Here's an overview of the ExtremeXP website, designed to provide an engaging and informative experience. From its sleek design to user-focused features, it showcases our innovative approach to data analytics and artificial intelligence.

4.1.1 Homepage

The homepage of ExtremeXP is visually appealing and structured in a way that guides users through the project's objectives, news updates, and core features.

Figure 4-1: ExtremeXP homepage

4.1.1.1 Header and Logo:

- **Logo:** The ExtremeXP logo is positioned at the top left, with the recognizable symbol representing the project's focus on experimentation, analytics, and user experience. It is paired with the text "ExtremeXP," which is in a bold, modern font. This logo sets the tone for the high-tech, innovative theme of the site.
- **Menu Navigation:** The menu bar includes clear, easy-to-read categories:
 - **Home:** The landing page of the ExtremeXP project site providing an overview of the project vision, key features, and latest news about activities and events.
 - **About:** Background information about the project's purpose, partners, structure, and objectives. This menu includes:
 - **The Project** – Explains the goals, motivation, and scope of the ExtremeXP framework.
 - **The Consortium** – Lists and describes the partners involved across Europe.
 - **Framework Components** – Details the building blocks of the ExtremeXP analytics ecosystem.

- **Use Cases** – Real-world applications and pilot demonstrations where the framework is applied.
 - **The Team** – Information on the research and development personnel behind the project.
- **Try the Framework:** Section focused on interactive experiments, practical tests, and engagement activities around the framework. Subitems include:
 - **Online Masterclass:** ExtremeXP Masterclass Replay – Access to recorded sessions or materials from an educational masterclass.
 - **Presentation of the beta-tests** – Overview or materials from beta testing rounds.
 - **Challenge 1: Core functionalities** – Challenge page where users can submit results for a core functional test.
 - **Challenge 2: Intents** – Submission for intents-focused challenge.
 - **Challenge 3: Analytics task library** – Contribution point for the task library challenge.
 - **Challenge 4: Visualization and Explainability** – Seen as a dedicated challenge involving visualization components.
 - **Challenge 5: DDM & Access Control** – Challenge focusing on data and access control mechanisms.
 - **Optional challenge: Experiment cards** – Additional optional challenge submission.
 - **Optional challenge: NFT Provenance** – Optional challenge linked with experiments and provenance.
 - **Optional challenge: Options Explorer** – Another optional challenge submission page.
 - **Challenge Materials** – Resources or materials supporting the above challenges.
- **Resources:** A hub for project outputs and related assets, often for researchers and developers. These include:
 - **Publications** – Academic papers or project reports produced from the ExtremeXP work.
 - **Deliverables** – Completed project deliverables (linked externally, e.g., on Zenodo).
 - **Software** – Software artifacts or code repositories relevant to the project.
 - **Partnerships** – Strategic collaborations and clusters (e.g., EU data initiatives).
 - **AI.BIG Cluster** – A specific research or innovation cluster tied to ExtremeXP.
 - **EUDATA+ cluster** – Another coordinated cluster involving data initiatives.
- **Communication:** Channels for project outreach, events, and communications.
 - **Events** – Upcoming or past events related to ExtremeXP.
 - **Branding** – Project branding guidelines and assets.
 - **Communication Tools** – Media or communication resources used by partners or stakeholders.
 - **Videos** – Video resources such as demos or presentations.
 - **Newsletter** – Signup or archive for project newsletters.
 - **Subscription** – Mechanism to subscribe to updates about the project.
- **Contact:** Basic contact information or a form to get in touch with the project team or consortium partners.
- **My account:** User account sections for site visitors who register or log in.
 - **Registration** – Create a new user account for interactive parts of the site.
 - **Connection** – Log in for users with existing credentials.

These links provide easy access to different sections of the website and are located at the top right, making navigation simple and user-friendly.

4.1.1.2 Main Banner Section

- **Background Design:** The background is a gradient of blue and green, creating a fresh, dynamic, and modern feel. The colours transition smoothly, reflecting the cutting-edge technology and experimental nature of ExtremeXP.
- **Text:** The main headline reads, "ExtremeXP proposes a new paradigm for data analytics." It is prominent and easy to read, grabbing the visitor's attention.
 - Below the headline, a subheading provides more context, explaining the project's focus on experiment-driven analytics and the goal of delivering precise, user-oriented outcomes.
- **Video Embed:** A YouTube video player is embedded below the text, showcasing the project's promotional video. The inclusion of a video helps visitors better understand the project's purpose and methodology visually.

4.1.1.3 Events Section

Figure 4-2: ExtremeXP News section example

- **Visual Layout:** The events are displayed in a grid layout with snippets ordered by ExtremeXP's most recent activities. Each snippet includes an image and a title that links to the full article.
- **Articles:** An article as a title, e.g., "EDBT 2025: Presenting GLOVES for Enhanced AI Explainability" a subtitle and Each article snippet is accompanied by a publication date, providing context on when the event or update took place.

4.1.1.4 Key Features Section

Figure 4-3: Key Features Section

- **Icons and Text:** This section is split into three columns, each describing one of the key features of ExtremeXP.
 - **A human-centered approach to AI and data-driven analytics:** This feature emphasizes how ExtremeXP puts the **end user** at the center of the process, focusing on their preferences, requirements, and decision-making.
 - **Experimentation is the core concept for generating extremely accurate analytics:** This highlights the innovative approach of using experimentation to create precise outcomes and insights for decision-making.
 - **User-driven Optimization of Complex Analytics:** This section elaborates on how ExtremeXP's framework optimizes analytics processes based on user profiles and needs, ensuring the results are accurate and efficient.

4.1.1.5 Footer

- **Links:** At the bottom of the page, the footer includes essential information such as links to the privacy policy, social media icons (LinkedIn, X), and the website's main contact email.
- **Partner and Sponsor Logos:** There are logos at the bottom indicating support and partnerships, such as those from the European Union (for funding) and research partners involved in the project.

4.1.1.6 Design and Usability

- **Typography:** The font used throughout the website is modern and clean, ensuring readability. It's also consistent, creating a cohesive visual experience.
- **Spacing and Layout:** The layout is highly organized with ample white space, ensuring that no section feels overcrowded. The content is well-spaced, making it easy for users to navigate and absorb information.
- **Responsiveness:** The website design is responsive, meaning it adjusts well to various screen sizes, making it accessible both on desktop and mobile devices.

- **Call-to-Action:** Buttons such as “More About the Project” are visible and encourage visitors to engage further with the content.

4.1.1.7 Overall Design and User Experience

- The overall feel of the website is modern, innovative, and user-centric, which aligns perfectly with the core values of ExtremeXP. The layout is clean, minimalistic, and very professional, ensuring that visitors can easily navigate the website and understand the key aspects of the project without feeling overwhelmed by too much information.

4.1.2 The Project Page

The **"The Project"** page in the About section of the ExtremeXP website provides a comprehensive overview of the project's objectives, methodology, and approach. Here's a detailed description of the page's layout, design, and content.

Figure 4-4: 'About' section

4.1.2.1 Header

- The header features the ExtremeXP logo and the navigation bar with links to other sections of the website, ensuring easy access to information throughout the site. This section remains consistent with the rest of the website, offering a clean and intuitive user experience.

4.1.2.2 Main Text: Introduction to the Project

- **Title:** "The Project" is displayed prominently at the top, providing immediate context for the page's content.
- **Introduction:** The first paragraph introduces the importance of data-driven insights for decision-making in various fields such as crisis management, predictive maintenance, and cybersecurity. It highlights the challenges involved in ensuring data insights are accurate, precise, and trustworthy, especially in critical domains.
- **Core Focus:** The text explains how ExtremeXP responds to these challenges by providing a new paradigm for data analytics, focused on experimentation-driven analysis. The goal is to integrate advanced technologies like AI, machine learning, and data integration into a system that places the user at the center of the decision-making process, ultimately improving outcomes through accurate, fit-for-purpose insights.

4.1.2.3 The Experimentation Approach

- **Modular Framework:** The page explains how ExtremeXP implements a **modular framework** that includes an **Experimentation Engine**, which orchestrates various components and subsystems related to modelling, planning experiments, and enhancing data.
- **Process Overview:** A detailed description is provided for how **user experience** and **decision-making** processes are integrated into the experimentation model. The goal is to ensure that **end-users' preferences**, feedback, and requirements are considered throughout the analytical workflow, creating a more user-centric approach to data analysis.

4.1.2.4 The Core Artifacts

Figure 4-5: Experimentation Approach section

- Below the description, the page introduces the **four core artifacts** of the ExtremeXP framework, each with a detailed explanation:
 - **User-driven AutoML:** Focuses on how the system uses machine learning algorithms, constraint-aware models, and continual learning strategies to ensure that model selection is driven by user preferences and requirements.

- **Transparent & Interactive Decision Making:** Highlights how the framework integrates interactive visualization, augmented reality (AR), and explainability techniques to provide users with clear insights and decision-making support.
- **Extreme Data & Knowledge Management:** Describes the system's approach to secure data management and knowledge sharing, ensuring the integrity and accessibility of data for analysis.
- **Analysis-aware Data Integration:** Addresses data integration challenges by automatically selecting alternative datasets and managing issues like missing, incomplete, and incorrect data points.

4.1.2.5 Visual Design

- **Colour Scheme:** The page features the same **blue and green gradient** used throughout the site, creating a cohesive, modern look. The colours are soft, professional, and clean, making the content easy to read and visually appealing.
- **Icons and Graphics:** Icons accompany each of the core features, providing a more **visual representation** of the different subsystems. A **flowchart diagram** visually explains how the various components of the ExtremeXP system interact with one another. The use of visuals helps break down complex information into easily digestible parts, making it more accessible to users.
- **Layout:** The page uses a well-organized layout with clear sections, making it easy for users to navigate and find the information they're looking for. Each section is separated by ample **white space**, which enhances readability and avoids clutter.

4.1.2.6 Key Features

Below the main description, the page lists **key features** of the project in three clear categories:

- **User-driven AutoML:** Discusses the algorithms and processes that enable the system to adapt and optimize based on user needs.
- **Transparent & Interactive Decision Making:** Focuses on making the decision process transparent and interactive for users.
- **Extreme Data & Knowledge Management:** Emphasizes secure data handling and management, essential for accurate analytics and outcomes.
- **Analysis-aware Data Integration:** Describes how the system tackles data quality issues and integrates various datasets to generate precise analytics.

Figure 4-6: Key Features section

4.1.3 Consortium Page

The ExtremeXP project brings together a consortium of 20 partners from 10 European countries, combining industrial, technological and academic expertise to develop advanced data analysis solutions. This page introduces each member of the consortium, companies, universities and research centres, and highlights their strategic role in building a collaborative ecosystem for precision decision-making.

4.1.4 Partnership Page

This page highlights ExtremeXP's key partnerships with European initiatives such as TEMA, CREXDATA and the Data Spaces Support Centre. It highlights the project's commitment to a wider collaborative approach, aimed at strengthening interoperability, data sharing and the impact of results on a European scale.

Figure 4-7: Consortium page

4.1.5 Team Page

In the ExtremeXP project, we believe that technology is above all about people. This page introduces you to our team, because you deserve to know who's working on your projects. You'll find passionate experts ready to turn your data into real solutions.

Figure 4-8: Partnerships page

4.1.6 Work Package Page

This page presents the concrete progress of our various Work Packages (WP). It highlights the results achieved by our teams and partners in key areas such as cybersecurity, user experience and data analysis.

Figure 4-9: Team page

Figure 4-10: WP page

4.2 Website Analytics

ExtremeXP has shown strong and accelerating growth in website traffic, reflecting increasing brand visibility and digital reach.

- 1.1 **+40% increase in returning users**, indicating improving engagement
- 2.1 Traffic is primarily driven by **Direct channels (around 80%)**, showing strong brand recognition and direct access
- 3.1 Referral, organic search, and email channels contribute a smaller but steadily developing share of traffic

The audience is international, with traffic coming from multiple regions across Europe and Asia, confirming ExtremeXP's expanding global exposure.

Key Takeaways

- 1. Strong percentage growth in acquisition

2. Increasing returning user rate
3. Solid direct traffic dominance
4. Growing international visibility

Conclusion

ExtremeXP's annual digital performance reflects a clear upward trajectory. The strong percentage growth in new and returning users demonstrates the effectiveness of current visibility and acquisition efforts.

While the project is still in its development phase, the current trends are very encouraging and position ExtremeXP on a solid path for continued expansion and optimization.

5 Social Media Channels

5.1 X

Figure 5-1: X social media channel

Visual identity and account presentation

- Username: @ExtremeXP_eu
- Bio: "EXperimentation driven and user eXperience-oriented analytics for eXtremely Precise outcomes and decisions – #horizoneurope project funded by the European Union."

→ This description presents the project acronym, its scientific focus (experimentation and user experience), and its funding by Horizon Europe.

Visual elements

- Profile photo: the official project logo, ensuring consistency with graphic and institutional materials.
- Banner: visual design in ExtremeXP colours, incorporating the logo and project name to reinforce immediate recognition.
- External link: official project website (extremexp.eu), facilitating redirection to more comprehensive information.

Positioning and objectives

The X account (formerly Twitter) plays a strategic role in project communication. It is a channel for rapid and instant dissemination of news. Its main objectives are:

- To provide real-time information on key project events and milestones.
- To increase visibility through hashtags and partner mentions.

- Participate in scientific and technological discussions already taking place on the platform.

Editorial strategy

- Nature of published content:
 - Event announcements and invitations,
 - Sharing of articles and scientific publications related to the project,
 - Retweets from partners to strengthen cohesion and collective visibility.
- Writing style: concise, impactful, adapted to the short and dynamic format of X; the use of emojis, images, infographics, and short videos help make the content attractive and engaging.
- Hashtags and tags: adoption of targeted keywords (#AI, #BigData, #DataAnalysis, #HorizonEurope, #Cybersecurity, etc.) to establish ExtremeXP in the relevant scientific and industrial communities.

5.2 LinkedIn

Figure 5-2: LinkedIn social media channel

Visual identity and page layout

- Page name: ExtremeXP
- Description: The page highlights the Horizon Europe ExtremeXP project, its partners, and its advances in the fields of artificial intelligence, data analysis, and crisis management. The description emphasizes the central objective: to develop an innovative approach to analysis guided by experimentation and user experience.
- Visual elements:
 - Official project logo as profile photo, ensuring immediate recognition.
 - Institutional banner using the ExtremeXP colours and graphic charter, consistent with official communication materials (website, presentations, flyers).
- External link: redirection to the official website (extremexp.eu), ensuring continuity with other information channels.

Positioning and objectives

The LinkedIn page plays a central role in ExtremeXP's professional and institutional communication. It has multiple objectives:

- To promote the project's results and deliverables to a qualified audience.

- To highlight the collaboration and partners of the consortium.
- To strengthen the scientific and industrial credibility of the project within the European ecosystem.
- Directly target researchers, industrialists, and decision-makers through a recognized channel for professional networking.

Editorial strategy

- Nature of published content:
 - Event announcements and invitations to follow the project's participation (trade shows, conferences, workshops).
 - Post-event reviews and summaries with photos and summaries.
 - Publications about deliverables, use cases (floods, explainable AI, cybersecurity, etc.) and scientific advances.
 - Testimonials or highlights from partners (laboratories, research institutes, companies).
 - Web articles, newsletters, etc.
- Writing style:
 - Informative, clear, structured, and tailored to a professional readership.
 - Institutional tone, highlighting expertise and results, but accessible to a wider audience.
- Visuals and media:
 - High-quality photos (plenary sessions, conferences, partner presentations).
 - Graphics, posters, infographics.
 - Video teasers from the YouTube channel, cross-posted.

5.3 YouTube

Figure 5-3: YouTube social media channel

Visual identity and channel presentation

- Channel name: ExtremeXP
- Description: The YouTube channel brings together all the audiovisual content produced as part of the project. It highlights
 - the objectives of ExtremeXP,
 - testimonials from partners,
 - and concrete results from use cases.
- Visual elements:
 - Project logo as profile photo to ensure consistency with other networks.
 - Banner featuring the official ExtremeXP graphic charter.
- External links: redirection to the official website and other networks (X and LinkedIn).

Positioning and objectives

- The YouTube channel is the project's main audiovisual channel. Its objectives are:
 - To present the project in an accessible and engaging way through video.
 - Highlight partners and their expertise through interviews.
 - Broadcast the promotional video illustrating ExtremeXP's ambitions and added value.
 - Serve as a multimedia support for other channels (LinkedIn, website, newsletters) that relay the videos.

Editorial strategy

- Nature of published content:
 - Interviews: each partner presents a specific aspect of the project (scientific, technological, crisis management, explainable AI, cybersecurity, etc.).
 - Promotional video: a short, impactful video presenting the ambition, innovations, and collaborative dimension of the project.
 - Event recordings: excerpts from conferences, trade show presentations, or plenary sessions, showing the project in action.
- Style and tone:
 - Educational and institutional, tailored to a professional audience but accessible to the general public.
 - The videos favour a clear, fast-paced format illustrated with dynamic visuals (subtitles, diagrams, images of the consortium).

6 Dissemination and Communication activities

6.1 Scientific Publications

All publications produced during the project are justified by the desire to promote, disseminate, and perpetuate the scientific and technological results obtained. They constitute an essential step in the recognition and integration of the project's advances within the scientific and professional community.

The ExtremeXP project partners have produced publications that pursue several objectives:

1. By proposing innovative approaches to the explainability, visualization, and analysis of artificial intelligence systems, they enrich the scientific literature and contribute to the development of new methods in a rapidly evolving field.
2. To serve as a vehicle for knowledge transfer to the scientific community, as well as to practitioners and industrial players who are likely to reuse or adapt the tools and methodologies developed.
3. Submitting results to conferences and specialized journals ensures their peer review, thus validating the relevance, robustness, and quality of the work carried out.

In short, these publications are not only academic deliverables, but also levers for promoting, legitimizing, and disseminating the project's results. They ensure scientific recognition, societal impact, and openness to future research and innovation prospects.

The following table lists the publications produced since the start of the project.

#	Authors	Title	Venue / Publication	Year	DOI / Link
1	Koen Kraaijveld, Claudia Raibulet	Adaptive Strategies Metric Suite	Springer	2023	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-64182-4_14
2	Rihan Hai et al.	Amalur: Data Integration Meets Machine Learning	ICDE	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE55515.2023.00301
3	Dimitris Sacharidis, Giorgos Giannopoulos, George Papastefanatos, Kostas Stefanidis	Auditing for Spatial Fairness	EDBT	2023	https://dx.doi.org/10.48786/edbt.2023.41
4	Milad Abdullah	Controlling Automatic Experiment Driven Systems Using Statistics and Machine Learning	ECSA	2023	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-36889-9_9
5	Rihan Hai et al.	Data Lakes: A Survey of Functions and Systems	TKDE	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2023.3270101
6	Milad Abdullah et al.	Early Stopping of Non-productive Performance	SEAA	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/SEAA60479.2023.00022

		Testing Experiments Using Measurement Mutations			
7	Joran Leest, Ilias Gerostathopoulos, Claudia Raibulet	Evolvability of Machine Learning based Systems: An Architectural Design Decision Framework	ICSAC	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSAC57050.2023.00033
8	K. Larnier et al.	Flash flood modelling and in urban areas using High Resolution hydrodynamic model and machine learning models	Fifth Space for Hydrology Workshop	2023	https://www.hydrospace2023.org/
9	S. Preetam et al.	An Approach for Intelligent Behaviour-Based Threat Modelling with Explanations	NFVSDN	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/NFVSDN59219.2023.10329587
10	Hendrik Jilderda, Claudia Raibulet	MAPE-K based Guidelines for Designing Reactive and Proactive Self-Adaptive Systems	Springer	2023	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66326-0_4
11	Vincent Gaudissart, Yasmine Boulfani, Kevin Larnier, Gwendoline Stephan, Jacques Coves, Christophe Triquet	METIS: An Open-Architecture for building AI-Ready Cloud platforms - Application to foster research on hydrological modelling	BiDS'23	2023	https://dx.doi.org/10.2760/46796
12	Claudia Raibulet, Xiaojun Ling	Non-Expert Level Analysis of Self Adaptive Systems	Springer	2023	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-0989-2_8
13	Michal Töpfer et al.	Online ML Self adaptation in Face of Traps	ACSOS	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACSOS58161.2023.00023
14	Wenbo Sun, Asterios Katsifodimos, Rihan Hai	An Empirical Performance Comparison between Matrix Multiplication Join and Hash Join on GPUs	ICDEW	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDEW58674.2023.00034
15	Danylo Khalyeyev, Tomáš Bureš, Petr Hnětynka	Towards a Reference Component Model of EdgeCloud Continuum	ICSAC	2023	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSAC57050.2023.00030
16	Faezeh Amou Najafabadi et al.	An Analysis of MLOps Architectures: A Systematic Mapping Study	Springer	2024	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70797-1_5
17	Joseph Giovanelli, Besim Bilalli, Alberto Abelló, Fernando SilvaCoira, Guillermo de Bernardo	Reproducible experiments for generating pre-processing pipelines for AutoETL	Information Systems Journal	2024	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2023.102314
18	Andra Ionescu et al.	AutoFeat: Transitive Feature Discovery over Join Paths	ICDE	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE60146.2024.00150
19	Gerard Pons, Miona Dimic, Besim Bilalli	Capturing Analytical Intents from Text	ADBIS	2024	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70421-5_8
20	Besim Bilalli et al.	There is no Data Science without Data Governance: A Proposal Based on Knowledge Graphs	DOLAP 2024	2024	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3653/panel1.pdf
21	Marc Maynou, Sergi Nadal	Discovery of Semantic Non-Syntactic Joins	DOLAP 2024	2024	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3653/short3.pdf
22	Nicollas R. de Oliveira et al.	Distributed Data Security in Digital Health: Self-Sovereign Identity, Access Control, and Blockchain-based Log Records	BCCA	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/BCCA62388.2024.10844453
23	Keerthiga Rajenthiram, Milad Abdullah, Ilias Gerostathopoulos,	ExpEngine: A Tool for Data Analytics Workflow Optimization Through User-Driven Experimentation	ACSOS-C 2024	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACSOS-C63493.2024.00058

	Petr Hnetyнка, Tomas Bures				
24	Joran Leest et al.	Expert Driven Monitoring of Operational ML Models	ACM	2024	https://doi.org/10.1145/3639476.3639771
25	Carolina Fernández et al.	Extending UEBA for Emerging Threats	GEANT Security Days	2024	https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/46796
26	Antonis Kontaxakis et al.	HYPPO: Using Equivalences to Optimise Pipelines in Exploratory ML	ICDE	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE60146.2024.00024
27	Gerard Pons et al.	Knowledge Graphs for Enhancing LLM Entity Disambiguation	Springer	2024	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77844-5_9
28	Md Ataur Rahman et al.	Mitigating Data Sparsity in Integrated Data through Text Conceptualization	ICDE	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE60146.2024.00269
29	Ziyu Li et al.	Model Selection with Model Zoo via Graph Learning	ICDE	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDE60146.2024.00088
30	Yiannis Verginadis et al.	NFT-based Data Provenance for AI Transparency in Enterprise Information Systems	Procedia Computer Science	2024	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.02.153
31	Keerthiga Rajenthiram	Optimizing Data Analytics Workflows through User-driven Experimentation	CAIN 2024	2024	https://doi.org/10.1145/3644815.3644971
32	Stavros Maroulis et al.	Partial Adaptive Indexing for Approximate Visual Analytics	BigVis 2024	2024	https://www.vldb.org/workshops/2024/proceedings/BigVis/BigVis2024_08.pdf
33	Albert Calvo et al.	RBD24: A labelled dataset with risk activities using log application data	Computers & Security	2024	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2024.104290
34	Faezeh Amou Najafabadi	Reference Architecture of MLOps Workflows	ECSA 2024	2024	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-71246-3_6
35	Milad Abdullah, Michal Topfer, Tomas Bures	Robin: A Systematic Literature Mapping Management Tool	SEAA 2024	2024	https://doi.org/10.1109/SEA64295.2024.00051
36	Nil Ortiz, Albert Calvo	Evaluating Robustness of Machine Learning Models against Adversarial Attacks: Techniques, Countermeasures, and Performance Analysis	JNIC	2024	https://hdl.handle.net/11441/159179
37	Kévin Larnier, et al.	Urban Flash Flood Prediction through High-Resolution Hydrodynamic Modelling and Machine Learning Approaches	IGARSS 2024, Conference Proceedings	2024	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10641091?signout=success&signout=success
38	Stavros Maroulis et al.	Visualization aware Time Series MinMax Caching	VLDB	2024	https://doi.org/10.14778/3659437.3659460
39	Milad Abdullah, David Georg Reichelt, Vojtech Horky, Lubomir Bulej, Tomas Bures, Petr Tuma	A Combined Approach to Performance Regression Testing Resource Usage Reduction	PROMISE '25	2025	https://doi.org/10.1145/3727582.3728690
40	Petr Hnetyнка, Tomas Bures, Ilias Gerostathopoulos, Milad Abdullah, Keerthiga Rajenthiram	A Model-Based Approach to Experiment-Driven Evolution of ML Workflows	MODELSWARD 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.5220/0013380500003896
41	Nikolaos Stamatopoulos, Vassilis Stamatopoulos,	Accelerating Entity Resolution through Vectorized Meta-Blocking on GPUs	ADBIS 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-05727-3_14

	Giorgos Alexiou, George Papastefanatos				
42	Keerthiga Rajenthiram et al.	AutoML: A Tertiary Study of Phases, Methods, Tools, and Frameworks	ECSA 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-04403-7_26
43	Georgia Gkioka, Dimitris Apostolou, Yiannis Verginadis, Gregoris Mentzas	Experiment Cards: A Documentation Framework for Trustworthy AI Experiments	ICTAI 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTAI66417.2025.00065
44	Stavros Maroulis, Vassilis Stamatopoulos, Panagiotis Gidakos et al.	ExperimentLens: Interactive Visual Analytics and Explainability for ML Experiment Management	Guide-AI @ VLDB 2025	2025	
45	Albert Calvo et al.	Explainable AI for Cybersecurity Decisions	Elsevier Book Chapter	2025	https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-44-329135-7.00018-7
46	Panagiotis Gidakos et al.	GLOVES: Global Counterfactual based Visual Explanations	EDBT	2025	https://openproceedings.org/2025/conf/edbt/paper-310.pdf
47	Panagiotis Gidakos et al.	GLOVES 2.0: Global Counterfactual-based Visual Explanations	SADIS Workshop	2025	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-04403-7_28
48	Michal Topfer, Tomas Bures, Frantisek Plasil, Petr Hnetyuka	Interpreting Workflow Architectures by LLMs	EASE 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.5220/0013358000003928
49	Keerthiga Rajenthiram	Optimizing Data Analytics Workflows Through User- Driven Experimentation: Progress and Updates	CAIN 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.1109/CAIN66642.2025.00035
50	Giorgos Alexiou et al.	QueryER: A Framework for Fast Analysis-Aware Deduplication over Dirty Data	EDBT	2025	https://doi.org/10.48786/edbt.2025.10
51	Ilias Gerostathopoulos et al.	Software Architecture for Data Intensive Systems Workshop	SADIS	2025	SADIS-workshop-proposal.pdf
52	P. Delporte, et al.	Surrogate Modelling and User- In-The-Loop Experimentation for Urban Flood Prediction: The ExtremeXP Approach	BIDS 2025	2025	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC143704
53	Milad Abdullah et al.	Temporal Harmonization of Heterogeneous Software Logs: A Unified Model for Time- Series Analysis	First International Workshop on Software Architectur e for Data- Intensive Systems	2025	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-04403-7_29
54	Vassilis Stamatopoulos, Stavros Maroulis, Christos Pantoleon, George Papastefanatos, Panos Vassiliadis	TimeVizBench: An Interactive Platform for Evaluating Techniques for Efficient Large Time Series Visualization	ADBIS 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-05727-3_8
55	Keerthiga Rajenthiram, Milad Abdullah, Ilias Gerostathopoulos,	Towards Continuous Experiment-driven MLOps	CAIN 2025	2025	https://doi.org/10.1109/CAIN66642.2025.00018

	Petr Hnetyнка, Tomas Bures, Gerard Pons				
56	P. Delporte, et al.	Urban Flash Flood Prediction Through High Resolution Deep Learning Approach	LPS 2025, Conference Proceedings.	2025	https://lps25.esa.int/lps25-presentations/presentations/1487/1487.pdf
57	Faezeh Amou Najafabadi, Justus Bogner, Ilias Gerostathopoulos, Patricia Lago	An architectural perspective on MLOps: Structures, processes, tools, and stakeholders	Information and Software Technology	2026	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2026.108029

Table 6-1: Scientific publications and papers

6.2 Open-Source Software

The ExtremeXP project has made its core software results openly available through its public repositories hosted on [GitHub repositories](#), including the final version (v1.0) of the ExtremeXP, enabling reproducibility, transparency, and further exploitation of the results. Details regarding the framework releases, including version numbers and corresponding components, are provided in Deliverable D6.2 Integrated ExtremeXP Framework and the official repo <https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON>.

The ExtremeXP GitHub organisation provides open-source access to the main project components, including the ExtremeXP Portal for experiment configuration and execution, the DSL Editor for workflow specification, the Experimentation Engine, the Decentralized Data Management layer, and supporting services such as visualization dashboards, access control, data abstraction, and intent capture and anticipation. All components are released under open-source licences, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and reusability, and enabling uptake, extension, and integration of ExtremeXP results by the wider research and innovation community.

6.3 Open Data and Open Access to ExtremeXP Results

In line with Horizon Europe Open Science and Open Data requirements, ExtremeXP has made a broad set of project results openly accessible through Zenodo, the EU-supported open research repository. The released datasets comply with the FAIR principles, ensuring that they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable by the wider research community.

The [ExtremeXP Zenodo community](#) hosts **multiple types of public project outputs**, including selected public deliverables and technical results. In particular, all five ExtremeXP use cases have been published in the form of open datasets with dedicated **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)**, ensuring long-term preservation, citability, and reuse by the research and innovation community. These datasets contain experiment specifications and workflows, input and output data, and experiment results (e.g. metrics). Below we present the description of the published datasets.

6.3.1 UC1 – Flash Flood Forecasting

This repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18786951>) groups the UC1 data-processing and machine-learning components used for flash-flood forecasting. It includes (i) a surrogate-model pipeline that trains and runs a neural emulator for flood quantities, (ii) a DEM super-resolution pipeline that learns to upscale elevation raster data, and (iii) a building-segmentation pipeline that extracts building footprints from point-cloud data and evaluates the results. At the top level, the code and specifications are organized by pipeline. The surrogate-model implementation is under CAW_Surrogate_Model/, including workflow specifications in Workflows/ and experiment specifications for training and inference in CAW1-Training/ and CAW2-Inference/. Task implementations are provided as Python entry points under Tasks/ (one folder per task) with per-task

dependencies in requirements.txt. The expected dataset structure is described in CAW_Surrogate_Model/Datasets/dataset.txt, and example results from executed runs are stored under CAW_Surrogate_Model/Exp Outputs/.

The DEM super-resolution pipeline is under CAW-DEM_SuperResolution/. The workflow and experiment definition is in Exp/CS_dem_sr.xxp and runs through reading a paired LR/HR dataset, splitting into train/validation sets, and training alternative model variants (ESRT and SwinIR) or evaluating a bicubic baseline. The input dataset archive referenced by the workflow is CAW-DEM_SuperResolution/Datasets/DATASET_DEM_SR.zip. The building-segmentation pipeline is under CAW_Building-Segmentation/. The workflow and experiment definition is in Exp/CS_building_segmentation.xxp and orchestrates reading point-cloud data, producing building polygons using two alternative segmentation variants (Alpha and DBSCAN), and evaluating the produced polygons. An example point-cloud input is available under CAW_Building-Segmentation/Datasets/ (clipped.las). The workflow specification references building_seg.zip as the input dataset artifact. Inputs are provided to the workflows as dataset archives referenced by the .xxp specifications (for example, the surrogate model uses an event dataset archive such as nimes_2005_v2.zip and a pretrained-model archive such as trained_models_2005.zip). Outputs include trained model checkpoints, evaluation metrics and predictions, and inference products. For the surrogate-model pipeline, example inference artifacts (prediction tables, exported features/labels, and archived raster outputs) and metrics spreadsheets are stored under CAW_Surrogate_Model/Exp Outputs/Exp Inference/, and example training metrics are stored under CAW_Surrogate_Model/Exp Outputs/Exp Training/.

Reproducibility is driven by the workflow/experiment specifications (.xxp) and the corresponding Python task implementations. Task definitions reference per-task virtual environments (requirements.txt) and commonly specify Python 3.12. During execution, some tasks write intermediate artifacts to a shared runtime directory (e.g., /shared/...) and then publish the declared final outputs via the workflow engine.

6.3.2 UC2 – Cybersecurity Situation Awareness

This dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18787517>) contains two workflows used in UC2 for cybersecurity situation awareness. CAW0 implements a data simulation pipeline: it creates a ThreatSim operation, generates a dataset through a Data Simulator API, optionally stores the generated dataset to DDM storage, and benchmarks the dataset by submitting it to the simulator's benchmarking endpoint. The datasets produced by CAW0 are stored under the CAW0/datasets_CAW0 directory. CAW1 implements an AI benchmarking pipeline: it reads a dataset (either from a local path or via DDM), splits it into training and test subsets, and benchmarks an existing model by computing standard classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC/AUC (with TPR/FPR). To reduce storage requirements, the CAW1 output feature matrices (X_train and X_test) are provided in compressed tar.gz form.

6.3.3 UC3 – PPDR Situational Intelligence and Decision Making

This dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18788551>) bundles the UC3 “Situational Intelligence for PPDR (ADS)” experimentation package, providing complete workflow/task specifications (ADS .xxp experiment files and per-task implementations for fire detection, alerting, user selection and user response across mobility contexts like walking/driving/cycling), the associated datasets and geo/user mock inputs, trained/inference-ready model artifacts (best.pt, YOLOv5/YOLOv8 weights), and produced evaluation outputs used to run, reproduce, and compare the end-to-end pipeline and its model performance reporting.

6.3.4 UC4 – Flexible Transportation

This dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18789819>) provides a high-level view of the UC4 flexible transportation scenario and the data it relies on; when opening this UC, a user can inspect the UC4_Exp1.xxp experiment to understand mobility scenario configuration, see the raw_locations_database.csv file to understand location/mobility data structure and type, read the Data Sharing Note to understand privacy/anonymisation/IP constraints on data and algorithms, and gain an overall understanding of flexible transportation evaluation in the project (though some detailed data and proprietary components cannot be shared).

6.3.5 UC5 - Failure Prevention for Manufacturing Industry

This dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18790046>) provides the data artifact(s), workflow specification, and example results for UC5 (failure prevention in a manufacturing setting). The objective is to learn a classifier from historical machine traces and use it to predict abnormal behaviour / failure risk on new machine files.

The folder includes an example machine/process time-series trace (input_data_*.csv). The file uses ';' as separator and contains a timestamp column (time) together with multiple sensor/process indicators (f1, f2, f3, f4). In the provided pipeline implementation, the indicator used for modelling is f3 (see the ReadData task implementation under Tasks/).

The workflow and experiment specification is provided as an .xxp descriptor in this folder. The main workflow executes an end-to-end ML pipeline with the following stages: ReadData -> DataAugmentation -> PrepareData (preprocessing) -> TrainModel -> EvaluateModel -> Explainability. The workflow references three external training datasets (provided via configured data projects). This deliverable folder includes an example input trace file plus the produced outputs/metrics, while the full training datasets are expected to be accessed through the configured data connections.

The pipeline is designed for three labelled categories of traces (not anomalous, electrical anomaly, mechanical anomaly). Training supports both multiclass and binary configurations and evaluates three model families: Neural Network (NN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The experiment logic runs a grid search over model hyperparameters across multiple search spaces, evaluates each candidate, and selects the best-performing model; if the multiclass performance is not satisfactory (threshold logic is defined in the control flow), the binary branch is executed and a best binary model is selected.

The Tasks/ folder contains the Python task implementations and their task descriptors. At a high level, the pipeline loads and labels datasets (ReadData), aligns variable-length time series and prepares tensors (AddPadding / PrepareData), creates train/test splits and derives dataset dimensions (SplitData), trains candidate models (TrainModelINN / TrainModelCNN / TrainModelRNN), computes evaluation metrics (EvaluateModel), and exports artefacts (train/test sets, predictions, and the trained model) for downstream analysis (Explainability).

Example results are included as a metrics summary (metrics.json) and an inference output file mapping each machine file name to a predicted class label (output_data_machine_predictions.csv).

6.4 Participation in Events

6.4.1 List of events

To enhance networking with third parties, each partner has actively engaged in at least two international events to promote ExtremeXP. The table below shows the events and workshops attended.

Type of activities	Partner	Title of event	URL	Date	Place
Meeting	ExtremeXP consortium	First ExtremeXP's Plenary meeting (ARC)	ExtremeXP – a new EU Horizon project - ExtremeXP	27-26th, January 2023	Athens, Greece
Meeting	ExtremeXP consortium	2nd ExtremeXP's Plenary meeting (TUDELFT)	The Consortium met and discussed the progress of the project during the plenary meeting in Delft. - ExtremeXP	September 2023	Delft, Netherlands
Exhibitions	AE	WAICF - World AI Cannes Festival	#1 AI Event for Business & Society World AI Cannes Festival 2023	2/11/2023	Cannes, France
Presentation	AE	SCS cluster working group AI and Data Analytics	https://www.pole-scs.org/2023/03/14/reunion-pleniere-du-groupe-de-travail-ia-data-analytics/	5/12/2023	France
Workshop	VUA	Participation and presentation at Bertinoro seminar on adaptive systems	Bertinoro_UCAS_seminar_report.pdf	6/10/2023	Italy
Presentation	ARC	"Get-to-know" introductory and welcome day from Data Spaces Support Centre	Get-to-know" introductory workshop and welcome day to HE Data projects (WP2021-22) BDVA	2/23/2023	Online
Conference, attendance, clustering	BS	OW2Con 23	https://www.ow2con.org/	6/14/2023 - 6/15/2023	Paris, France
Seminar, presentation	BS	Polytechnico de Milan/ CherryData	https://www.cherry-data.com/	7/11/202 - 7/12/2023	Milan, Italy
Workshop	CS	Participation to "hydrospace 2023" workshop for abstract presentation	https://www.hydrospace2023.org/	27/11/2023	Lisbon, Portugal
Conference Participation	ARC	26th International Conference on Extending Database Technology (EDBT 2023)	http://edbticdt2023.cs.uoi.gr/	2/23/2023	Ioannina, Greece
Full day of conferences	CS	Participation to 3ème édition de Future Intelligence	https://futureintelligence.tech	11/7/2023	Toulouse, France
European Ecosystem Event	BS, ICCS, UL	EBDVF	https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/2023-edition/	25/10/2023- 27/10/2023	Valencia, Spain

Presentation	ARC	Presentation of ExtremeXP in AI 4 Sustainability Webinar organized by Sister Project TEMA	https://extremexp.eu/elementor-922/	11/15/2023	Webinar
Conference	BS	Open-Source Experience Paris 2023	https://www.opensource-experience.com/	6-7/12/2023	Paris, France
Conference	i2CAT	Paper Accepted and Presented at IEEE NFV-SDN	https://nfvsdn2023.ieee-nfvsdn.org/	7/11/2023	Dresden, Germany
University Lecture	ARC	G. Papastefanatos presented the project as part of a lecture in Visual Analytics course in the 2023 class of the MSc on Cybersecurity and Data Science, Department of Informatics, University of Piraeus	https://cybersecdatasci.cs.unipi.gr/the-msc/about-the-msc/	6/5/2023	Athens Greece
Conference Proceedings	CS	Participation to the conference Proceedings Big Data from Space 2023 for paper presentation	https://www.bigdatafromspace2023.org/	6-9/11/2023	Vienna
Workshop	TUD	Participation and presentation at IFIP Summer School 2023	https://ifip-summerschool.github.io/	8-11/8/2023	Oslo
Presentation	ITU	ExtremeXP: desafiaments i solucions a la detecció d'amenaçes en temps real	https://esdeveniments.upc.edu/103239/programme/jornada-tic-2023.html	12/12/2023	Barcelona, Spain
Conference Proceedings	i2CAT	Paper submission to JNIC 2024	Call-For-Papers – JNIC 2024	2023-2024	Spain, TBD
Online workshop	ARC	LDS Technology Workshop	https://dssc.eu/space/News/blog/256802840/Legislation+and+regulation+for+data+spaces%3A+A+n+environment+to+foster+data+sharing+and+AI+development	29/01/2024	Online
Exhibitions	AE	WAICF - World AI Cannes Festival	#1 AI Event for Business & Society February 13-15, 2025 in Cannes	February 2024	Cannes, France
Conference	i2CAT	Presentation of "Extending UEBA for emerging threat, detection, characterization and intelligence generation"	https://events.geant.org/event/1515/	9-11/4/2024	Prague, Czech Republic

Conference Proceedings	CS	Participation at IGARSS 2024 for paper presentation	https://www.grss-ieee.org/news-2/igarss-2024-to-be-held-in-athens-2/	11-18/10/2024	Athens, Greece
Workshop	i2CAT	Paper submission to SecSoft 2024	secsoft-workshop.org/cfp.html	2024	Europe, TBD
Conference Participation	ICCS	Symposium On Applied Computing (SAC 2024), Information Architecture Conference (IAC 2024), Conference on Innovative Data Systems Research, International Research on Data Engineering (ICDE), Intelligent Information Systems and Applications (IISA)	SAC 2024 IAC 2024 – IAC: Information Architecture Conference IEEE ICDE 2025 IISA 2024	April 2024	N/A
Conference	i2CAT	Presentation of "Extending UEBA for emerging threat, detection, characterisation and intelligence generation"	https://events.geant.org/event/1515/	9-11/4/2024	Prague, Czech Republic
Workshop	ARC	ExtremeXP and AI. BigData cluster to support\sponsor the BigVis 2024 -7th International Workshop on Big Data Visual Exploration and Analytics August 29, 2024, VLDB 2024 Guangzhou, China	VLDB 2024 - 50th International Conference on Very Large Data Bases	8/29/2024	Guangzhou, China
Conference Presentation	VUA	Optimizing Data Analytics Workflows through User-driven Experimentation	Optimizing Data Analytics Workflows through User-driven Experimentation IEEE Conference Publication IEEE Xplore	15/04/2024	Lisbon, Portugal
Presentation in a H2020 Project meeting	TUD	Guiding Light in the AI Landscape: Illuminating the Path to a Trustworthy AI Ecosystem	https://spatial-h2020.eu/spatial-final-event-in-delft/	1/7/2024	Delft, NL
Presentation	IDK	ExtremeXP UC: Failure prevention for manufacturing industry use case	https://biemh.bilbaoexhibitioncentre.com/en/	6/7/2024	Bilbao, Spain
Meeting	ExtremeXP consortium	3rd ExtremeXP's Plenary meeting (CS GROUP Sopra Steria)	Plenary session: Progress and demonstrations by ExtremeXP's Team - ExtremeXP	From 11 to 12, April 2024	Sophia Antipolis, France
Workshop	ExtremeXP consortium	Consortium Technical workshop (Intracom)	https://extremexp.eu/2024/06/19/horizon-europe-technical-workshop-in-athens-with-intracom/	12 th -14 th of June 2024	Athens, Greece

Conference	BU	Adapting Random Simple Recurrent Network for Online Forecasting Problems	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10570020	5/23/2024	Madrid, Spain
Presentation	VU	ACSOS 2024	ACSOS 2024	Mon 16 - Fri 20 September 2024	Aarhus, Denmark
Presentation	VU	ECSA 2024	Program - ECSA 2024	Tue 3 - Fri 6 September 2024	Luxembourg
Meeting	ExtremeXP consortium	4th ExtremeXP's Plenary meeting (UPC)	-	From 05 to 06, November, 2024	Barcelona, Spain
Presentation	IDK	ExtremeXP UC: Failure prevention for manufacturing industry use case	https://www.ifema.es/metalmadrid	11/20/2024	Madrid, Spain
Presentation	IDK	MetalMadrid 2024	METALMADRID 2025, Feria del metal IFEMA MADRID	20-21 November 2024	Madrid, Spain
Exhibitions	ADS	Open-Source Paris 2024	Open-Source Experience - OPEN SOURCEZ VOS SOLUTIONS IT!	4-5 December 2024	Paris
Short Course/Tutorial	CS	Big Data Analytics for Natural Disaster Management	Short Course/Tutorial on Big Data Analytics for Natural Disaster Management – Icarus CVML Research	03 December 2024	Online
Collaboration	ExtremeXP consortium	Cluster EUDATA+	Cluster – DATAMITE	12/2024	Permanent
Presentation	ARC	ExtremeXP overview presentation in the Plenary of Autofair Project - (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070568)	https://humancompatibile.org/	1/23/2025	Athens Greece
Presentation	BS	La French Tech Côte d'Azur	https://www.frenchtechcotedazur.fr/	2/7/2025	Auron, France
Exhibitions	AE	WAICF - World AI Cannes Festival	#1 AI Event for Business & Society February 13-15, 2025 in Cannes	13-15 February 2025	Cannes, France

Presentation	BS	Salon Cloud Security	https://www.salon-cloud-security.com/	3/19/2025	Paris, France
Conference Presentation	ARC	GLOVES: Global Counterfactual-based Visual Explanations	https://edbticdt2025.upc.edu/?contents=main.html	25-28 March 2025	Barcelona, Spain
Symposium event	CS	Participation to Living Planet Symposium 2025 for abstract presentation	https://lps25.esa.int/	23—27 JUNE 2025	VIENNA, AUSTRIA
Exhibitions	ARC/BS/ICOM	BDVA's Data Week	https://data-week.eu/2025-edition/call-for-dw-workshops-sessions/	5/27/2025	Athens Greece
Conference Presentation	VUA & CUNI	ExpEngine: A Tool for Data Analytics Workflow Optimization through User-Driven Experimentation	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10766102	18/09/2024	Aarhus, Denmark
Conference Presentation	VUA & CUNI & UPC	Towards Continuous Experiment-driven MLOps	https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.03455	18/09/2024	Ottawa, Canada
Conference Presentation	VUA & CUNI & UPC	Optimizing Data Analytics Workflows through User-driven Experimentation: Progress and Updates	https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.03455	18/09/2024	Ottawa, Canada
Meeting	ExtremeXP consortium	5th ExtremeXP's Plenary meeting (SINTEF)	Highlights from Oslo: ExtremeXP's Plenary Marks a Major Milestone - ExtremeXP	May 2025	Oslo, Norway
Poster	i2CAT	Extended abstract of RBD24: A Labelled Dataset with Risk Activities Using Log Application Data Santiago Escuder Folch, Albert Calvo, Nil Ortiz, Oriol Graupera-Serra, Josep Escrig and Maxime Compastié	https://2025.jnic.es/	{4,5,6}/06/2025	Zaragoza, Spain
Conference Proceedings	CS	Participation to conference Proceedings Big Data from Space 2025 for paper presentation	https://www.bigdatafromspace2025.org/	7/5/2025	Vienna
Conference Presentation	ARC	QueryER: A Framework for Fast Analysis-Aware Deduplication over Dirty Data	https://acmsigmod.gr/hdms/2025/	7/4/2025	Ioannina, Greece

Webtech	BS/I2CA	Aktantis	Comment prendre des décisions fiables et précises à partir de données	19/09/25	Meeting
Conference Presentation	ARC	VLDB25	VLDB 2025 - 51st International Conference on Very Large Data Bases	September 1-5, 2025	London, United Kingdom
Conference Presentation	ARC	GLOVES 2.0: Global Counterfactual-based Visual Explanations	https://sadis2025.smartarch.cz/#submissions	9/16/2025	Limassol, Cyprus
Conference Presentation	ARC	ADBIS 2025	ADBIS - Main Page	September 23-26 2025	Tampere, Finland
Summer School	UL	Human–AI Summer School & Doctoral Symposium – University of Ljubljana 2025	https://datatrust.fri.uni-lj.si/summer-school/	September 22 to 26, 2025	Ljubljana, Slovenia
Exhibitions	ABS	131ème congré national	https://congres2025.pompier.fr/	October 8-11, 2025	Le Mans, France
Conference Presentation	ICCS	37th International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI 2025)	ICTAI 2025	From 3 to 5 November 2025	Athens, Greece
Exhibitions	ARC	European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2025	EBDVF Data and AI Event	November 12 to 14, 2025	Copenhagen, Denmark
Presentation	I4D	Sophia Summit 2025	SOPHIA SUMMIT 2025 - Université Côte d'Azur	November 19 to 21, 2025	Sophia Antipolis, France
Meeting	ExtremeXP consortium	Final ExtremeXP Plenary Meeting (ICCS)	ExtremeXP Final Plenary Meeting in Athens - ExtremeXP	December 2 to 4, 2025	Athens, Greece
Conference Presentation	ABS	Presentation to AI Experts from Internal Departments	-	December 2025	Internal departments?

Presentation	ABS	Project Presentation to Future Users of the Public Safety Collaboration System (Post-baccalaureate students)	-	January 2026	Higher school Campus
Demonstration	ABS	Demonstration of the Collaboration Platform and ExtremeXP to Students	-	April 2026	Higher school Campus
Masterclass	ExtremeXP consortium	ExtremeXP Online Masterclass	Online Masterclass - ExtremeXP	February 9th, 2026	Online
Exhibitions	I4D	World AI Cannes Festival (WAICF)	#1 AI Event for Business & Society February 12-13, 2026 in Cannes	February 12 and 13, 2026	Cannes, France

Table 6-2: Participation in Events

6.4.2 Communication Process and Event Example Templates

The project's communication strategy was shaped by input from all partners, who completed an event template to create content for social media and the project website. Key areas covered include:

- Conference details (title, date)
- Target audience (Industry professionals, researchers in AI and data science, and policy makers focused on AI regulation).
- Contribution information (abstract, presentation)
- Article publication via ExtremeXP channels (web portal, news, social networks)
- Networking (key individuals, noted stakeholders)

Below is an example of a filled template, which illustrates how partners documented their activities for communication purposes.

For additional reference, Appendix contains further examples of promotion event templates that have been completed by other project partners.

Event Name	EUROPEAN BIG DATA VALUE FORUM	Event Organizer	BDVA
Location	VALENCIA	Start date / End date	25/10/23 to 27/10/23
Link to the event	Programme - European Big Data Value Forum		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Iyad Alshabani	BitSparkles	Participant
Yiannis Verginadis	ICCS	Participant

Dimitris Apostolou	ICCS	Participant
<p>Rationale for Participation: <i>Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?</i></p>		
<p>The event focused on big data and its evolution. It was a great learning experience for ExtremeXP, as the project is very much about data.</p>		
<p>LinkedIn Post</p>		
<p><i>The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organizer, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.</i></p>		
<p>The #EBDVF 2023 took place from October 25 to 27, 2023, organized by #BDVA Big Data Value Association in Valencia.</p>		
<p>This flagship event of the European megadata value community, as well as industrial research and innovation in the field of AI.</p>		
<p>This year's theme is "Data and AI in Action: Sustainable impact and future realities" ExtremeXP partners, BitSparkles ICCS and University of Ljubljana attended the different sessions and participated to the great discussions and synergies in research and innovations related to ExtremeXP domains such as #AI #BigData #HPC #EuropeanDataSpacesandCloud #CloudComputing</p>		
<p>Corporate presentation of the event</p>		
<p><i>Report here the official presentation of the event</i></p>		
<p>Welcome to the flagship event of the European Big Data Value and Data-Driven AI Research and Innovation community!</p> <p>The European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policymakers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions, and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI.</p> <p>This year, the event will take place in Valencia, Spain on 25 – 27 October.</p> <p>The EBDVF 2023 is organized by the Big Data Value Association (BDVA), in collaboration with INCLIVA VLC (Biomedical Research Institute), ITI (Investigate to Innovate), Polytechnic University of Madrid (Universidad Politecnica de Madrid) Polytechnic University of Valencia (Universitat Politecnica de Valencia) and the European Commission (DG CNECT). It has been granted with the Spanish Presidency Auspice.</p> <p>The EBDVF 2023 is organized by the Big Data Value Association (BDVA), in collaboration with INCLIVA VLC (Biomedical Research Institute), ITI (Investigate to Innovate), Polytechnic University of Madrid (Universidad Politecnica de Madrid) Polytechnic University of Valencia (Universitat Politecnica de Valencia) and the European Commission (DG CNECT). It has been granted with the Spanish Presidency Auspice.</p>		
<p>Illustration of the event (logo/picture)</p>		
<p><i>Report here the official illustration of the event</i></p>		

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS

It was great to talk to all the participants; it was great to talk to all the participants and learn even more about the advances in Big Data and learn even more about the advances in Big Data.

Table 6-3: Promotion event templates

6.5 ExtremeXP Master Class and Beta Test Campaign

6.5.1 ExtremeXP Online Master Class

The [ExtremeXP Online Master Class](#) took place on Monday, 9 February 2026, from 10:00 to 13:00 CET, and was delivered as a live session via Microsoft Teams. The event attracted 33 participants, drawn from project partners and academic user communities, and was designed for professionals, researchers, and stakeholders with an interest in data-driven experimentation, advanced analytics, and intelligent decision-making frameworks. The entire session was recorded to allow asynchronous access for interested parties unable to attend in person.

The programme covered the ExtremeXP framework in a comprehensive and progressive manner, moving from foundational concepts and system architecture through to individual platform components, practical demonstrations, and an assessment of innovation potential. Two interactive feedback sessions using Mentimeter polling were embedded in the agenda to gather participant impressions and facilitate dialogue with the presenters. The full agenda is presented in the table below.

Figure 33 ExtremeXP Online Master Class

Time (CET)	Topic	Presenter / Organisation
10:00 – 10:10	Introduction: ExtremeXP motivation, concepts and use cases	George Papastefanatos, Athena Research Center
10:10 – 10:20	The architecture of the ExtremeXP framework	Ilias Gerostathopoulos, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

10:20 – 10:40	Experimentation engine, domain-specific language (DSL) and execution engines	Ilias Gerostathopoulos, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
10:40 – 11:00	Data abstraction layer and DSL editor	Milad Ashqi Abdullah, Charles University in Prague
11:00 – 11:20	Experiment Monitoring, Analysis and Explainability	Stavros Maroulis, Athena Research Center
11:20 – 11:30	Feedback from participants (Mentimeter session)	Orestis Almpanoudis, ICCS
11:30 – 11:40	Break	
11:40 – 12:00	Decentralised Data Management	Orestis Almpanoudis, ICCS
12:00 – 12:10	Experiment Cards	Georgia Gkioka, ICCS
12:10 – 12:25	Intent-driven experimentation	Besim Bilalli, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
12:25 – 12:40	Options Explorer	Kristina Veljkovic, University of Ljubljana
12:40 – 12:50	Value and innovation potential of the ExtremeXP framework	Iyad Alshabani, BitSparkles
12:50 – 13:00	Feedback from participants (Mentimeter session)	

The Master Class served as a key dissemination action for the project, enabling direct engagement with external audiences and providing a structured opportunity to explain the value and applicability of the ExtremeXP platform to users beyond the consortium.

6.5.2 ExtremeXP Beta Test Campaign

In parallel with the Master Class, ExtremeXP conducted a Beta Test Campaign as part of Milestone 5. The campaign was designed to validate the ExtremeXP framework with external users and to generate substantive feedback from participants operating independently of the project consortium. The Beta Test Campaign was structured around five core challenges and three optional challenges, made available to external participants for testing and evaluation:

- [Challenge 1 – Core functionalities](#)
- [Challenge 2 – Intents](#)
- [Challenge 3 – Analytics task library](#)
- [Challenge 4 – Visualization and Explainability](#)
- [Challenge 5 – DDM & Access Control](#)

In addition, participants could opt to take on one or more of the following optional challenges:

- [Optional challenge: Experiment Cards](#)
- [Optional challenge: NFT Provenance](#)
- [Optional challenge: Options Explorer](#)

Participants were invited to register and access the ExtremeXP framework through a dedicated [registration form](#) on the project website, which allowed them to indicate their profile, use case, and areas of interest. Based on this information, an appropriate testing environment was configured and made available. Registrants gained access to the full ExtremeXP framework map, with the freedom to explore and experiment with the components most relevant to their needs. The campaign contributed to both the quality assurance of the platform and the broader engagement objectives of the ExtremeXP communication strategy.

Unleashing the Power of Experiment-Driven Analytics

The ExtremeXP framework introduces a new paradigm for how organizations design, execute, and optimise complex analytics. By combining modularity, automation, user-centric design, and explainability, ExtremeXP transforms data-intensive experimentation into an efficient, transparent and interactive process. Our approach is built on a modular architecture capable of orchestrating multiple advanced subsystems. At its core lies the Experimentation Engine, which acts as the central driver for modelling experiments, enriching them with semantic and contextual information, scheduling analytics workflows across available infrastructures, and monitoring execution in real time. This engine is delivered as a service, supporting scalable and fully traceable experimentation.

[Register and try our framework](#)

The ExtremeXP Framework Tools & Capabilities

Below is an overview of the main subsystems and their unique capabilities, aligned with the XP vision of transparent, interactive, and user-driven analytics.

Figure 5 ExtremeXP Beta Testing Campaign

6.6 ExtremeXP Summer School

The Human–AI Summer School & Doctoral Symposium was organised by the University of Ljubljana in partnership with the ExtremeXP project, and took place in Ljubljana, Slovenia from 22 to 26 September 2025. The event offered an intensive five-day educational and collaborative environment for researchers, doctoral students, and practitioners working at the intersection of artificial intelligence and human-centred computing, and was offered free of charge to all accepted participants.

The programme was designed to combine theoretical depth with practical engagement, and addressed a range of advanced topics directly aligned with the ExtremeXP research agenda, including human–AI interaction, ethical and transparent AI, decision-making frameworks, and blockchain-based trust mechanisms. The event was structured around the following activities:

- Hands-on workshops covering AI data visualisation, decision models, ExtremeXP scientific workflows, and AI-supported decision processes
- Keynote lectures by renowned European experts in human–AI interaction, ethical and transparent AI, and decision-making frameworks
- Doctoral Symposium, providing early-stage researchers with an opportunity to present their work, receive expert feedback, and engage with senior members of the research community
- Collaborative team projects addressing defined research challenges, evaluated by a panel of domain experts
- Micro-certificates, awards, and constructive feedback for outstanding contributions
- Optional seaside excursion to Izola and Piran for participants wishing to extend their networking activities beyond the formal programme

The Summer School served a dual role as both a high-quality training event for the next generation of researchers and a dissemination vehicle for ExtremeXP results and tools. By embedding project outcomes into a structured educational setting, the event contributed to the broader goals of community building, knowledge transfer, and long-term engagement with the research community beyond the project's immediate consortium.

Impact and Dissemination Value

The Summer School contributed to:

- Increasing the visibility of the ExtremeXP project at European level
- Disseminating project methodologies and frameworks to early-stage researchers
- Strengthening academic and cross-institutional collaboration
- Supporting capacity building in Trustworthy Human–AI systems
- Engaging the next generation of researchers in interdisciplinary AI research

The event served as a key dissemination and community-building activity within the ExtremeXP communication strategy.

Communication and Outreach

The event was promoted through ExtremeXP’s official communication channels:

Official web article: <https://extremexp.eu/2025/09/14/human-ai-summer-school-doctoral-symposium-ljubljana-2025/>

LinkedIn announcement: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/extremexp_humanai-summerschool-doctoralsymposium-activity-7378396512927555584-_Zsn?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAADmwsMQB61L1IEUDXi7sTaW-e2S0BixQYQM

LinkedIn prepost https://www.linkedin.com/posts/extremexp_humanai-summer-school-doctoral-symposium-activity-7375823517763936256-csoD?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAADmwsMQB61L1IEUDXi7sTaW-e2S0BixQYQM

Figure 6 Human–AI Summer School & Doctoral Symposium

6.7 Liaison Activities with other related EU-funded project

ExtremeXP aims to connect and collaborate with other initiatives where possible to support its work and outcomes. Project partners have actively joined various meetups and events to foster these collaborations. The following table lists several cluster projects targeted for potential partnerships.

Project	Short Description
EUDATA+ Cluster	<p>ExtremeXP is part of the EUDATA+ Cluster, a collaborative initiative supported by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme. The cluster gathers seven European projects working on data monetisation, exchange, interoperability, and value creation. Its goal is to align expertise, foster knowledge transfer, and maximise collective impact within the European data economy through scientific collaboration, technical synergies, business strategies, and real-world pilots.</p> <p>Projects within the EUDATA+ Cluster:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ExtremeXP • PISTIS • FAME • UPCAST • enRichMyData • Graph-Massivizer • DATAMITE
AI.BIG Cluster	<p>ExtremeXP is part of the AI.BIG Cluster a collaborative initiative focused on leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Big Data for emergency situation management and extreme data exploitation. The cluster addresses the growing challenges posed by natural disasters, health crises, maritime emergencies, forest fires, flash floods, cybersecurity threats, and transportation disruptions, offering authorities and humanitarian organizations advanced tools for prediction, preparedness, and response. By combining predictive algorithms, machine learning, and big data analytics, the cluster aims to improve accuracy, prediction, and prevention of emergencies, enabling early warnings, real-time situational awareness, and optimized resource management.</p> <p>Projects within the AI.BIG Cluster:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ExtremeXP • TEMA • CREXDATA
Data Spaces Support Centre	<p>The Data Spaces Support Centre, funded by the European Commission under the Digital Europe Program, supports initiatives and companies aiming to create sovereign data spaces. The Centre works to understand stakeholders' needs, define common requirements, and establish best practices to accelerate the development of interoperable, trusted, and value-generating data ecosystems across sectors. ExtremeXP participates as a Research and Innovation project, contributing to the development of these data spaces and promoting the reuse of data while fully respecting EU values. This initiative is a key driver of digital transformation in Europe, enabling collaboration, innovation, and economic growth through secure and open data sharing</p>
Data Nexus Cluster in DATA Week	<p>At Data Week 2025 in Athens, ExtremeXP actively contributed to discussions on data trading and pricing models in the era of Artificial Intelligence. The project participated in the event organised by the DataNexus project cluster, strengthening collaboration within the European data innovation ecosystem.</p> <p>As data becomes a strategic economic asset, defining fair valuation mechanisms, sustainable monetisation models, and trusted exchange frameworks is essential for building robust and scalable Data Spaces. ExtremeXP brought its expertise in AI-driven experimentation orchestration, demonstrating how structured</p>

	<p>experimentation can optimise data value chains, support data valuation processes, and enhance transparency in AI-based environments. The project also highlighted advanced approaches to data provenance and traceability, reinforcing trust in emerging data monetisation models. Beyond Data Week 2025, ExtremeXP has maintained close collaboration with the EUDATA+ initiative through joint events and coordinated activities at BDVA 2024, BDVA 2025, and Data Week (May 2025), further consolidating synergies across European data projects and contributing to the development of a competitive and trustworthy Single Digital Market for data.</p>
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Table 6-4: Synergies with other projects

6.8 Standardisation activities

6.8.1 Standardisation approach

Standardisation aspects are addressed in a monitoring and alignment perspective throughout the ExtremeXP project. The consortium follows relevant international and European standards applicable to the project domain, in particular those related to interoperability, data exchange, software engineering practices, and system interfaces. When appropriate, existing standards and reference frameworks are taken into account in the design and implementation of project outputs, with the objective of ensuring compatibility with existing ecosystems and facilitating future reuse and integration.

Although ExtremeXP does not aim to develop, propose, or formally submit new standards or specifications, its results and technical practices may contribute to informing standardisation activities by providing feedback, lessons learned, and best practices that can be shared within relevant research, industrial, and stakeholder communities.

6.8.2 Project specific contributions to standardisation

6.8.2.1 Participation in BDVA Task Force on Standards

ExtremeXP has been connected to standardisation activities primarily through its involvement in the **Big Data Value Association (BDVA)** ecosystem, and in particular through the **BDVA Task Force for Standards**.

ExtremeXP partners were **invited to participate in selected discussions and consultations**, allowing the project to:

- monitor ongoing standardisation initiatives related to **data spaces, interoperability, AI, and data governance**,
- **review and provide feedback** on draft documents and position papers prepared within the BDVA Task Force,
- ensure that the architectural and methodological choices developed in ExtremeXP remained **aligned with emerging European frameworks and best practices**.

This monitoring and feedback-oriented participation enabled ExtremeXP to stay consistent with the evolving BDVA standardisation landscape, while avoiding the creation of project specific or isolated approaches. The project therefore contributed indirectly, by validating and reinforcing.

Contribution of Use Cases to domain specific standardisation activities

Several UCs were **naturally connected to domains where standards, reference architectures, and best practices already exist**, such as:

- data management and interoperability,

- artificial intelligence and explainability,
- cybersecurity and trust frameworks,
- Earth Observation and crisis management ecosystems.

Through their participation in **scientific conferences, industrial workshops, clustering activities, and European initiatives** (e.g. BDVA, EUDATA+, AI.BIG, Data Spaces Support Centre), the Use Case partners contributed to:

- the **validation of existing standards and reference frameworks** in real operational contexts,
- the identification of **gaps and limitations** when applying these frameworks to extreme data and AI driven workflows,
- the dissemination of **lessons learned and best practices** that are relevant for standardisation communities.

These contributions remain indirect, but they support standardisation efforts by providing **evidence-based feedback** from concrete implementations, which is a key input for the evolution of standards in data intensive and AI driven domains.

6.8.2.2 *Links with data and telecommunications standardisation bodies through consortium partners*

Some ExtremeXP partners, including **ICOM**, have independent activities and longstanding involvement with **standard bodies and industry groups** related to data management, digital infrastructures, and telecommunications.

Their expertise and background contributed to ExtremeXP by:

- bringing awareness of **relevant standards and ongoing initiatives** in data and telco domains,
- ensuring that project developments remained **compatible with established industrial practices**,
- supporting alignment with broader European digital and data strategies.

More specifically, ICOM's active participation in relative to ExtremeXP standardization bodies and its activities is the following:

- **AIOTI** (Alliance for AI, IoT and Edge Continuum Innovation) WG Standardization - ExtremeXP has been included in the [report on IoT and Edge Computing EU Funded Projects Landscape Release 3](#), which is dated 22-Jan-2025. The main objective of this deliverable is to provide the landscape of EU funded projects focusing on IoT and edge computing, which can be used to:
 - leverage on existing IoT and edge computing research and innovation activities in Europe, and
 - provide input to IoT and edge computing standardization gap analysis activities.
- **TMF-AIOps** (TM Forum's AI Operations) – Since the beginning of the project ICOM participated in the [AIOps autonomous service assurance](#) Catalyst project. This Catalyst demonstrates how AI can drive closed-loop service assurance in communications service providers' network services, building the foundations for autonomous networks. Among others, the project demonstrates concrete AI-based use cases covering vital assurance processes, including prediction of potential faults and prevention of impacts on business services
- **ETSI-ENI/CIM** - ICOM continues its involvement in several ETSI working groups (ENI, CIM, ZSM, NFV etc.) as observer, with aim to identify possible correlations with ExtremeXP activities for

possible contribution and/or bringing in information about relevant standard developments of possible interest to the ExtremeXP operations.

6.8.3 Overall Assessment of Standardisation Activities

In summary, ExtremeXP addressed standardisation **from an alignment and monitoring perspective** rather than through direct standard creation. The project ensured consistency with European initiatives and best practices by:

- engaging with BDVA and related ecosystems,
- leveraging feedback from Use Cases operating in standard intensive domains,
- capitalising on consortium partners' experience with standard bodies.

This approach is fully consistent with the project's objectives and maturity level, and supports the **reusability, interoperability, and long-term sustainability** of ExtremeXP results.

7 Dissemination and Communication Impact Assessment

The success of the communication and dissemination actions has been evaluated throughout the project duration based on specific metrics, according to the GA that summarize the project results at month M36.

7.1 Dissemination and Communication Monitoring

The following table shows the dissemination KPIs that were monitored and measured throughout the project:

Dissemination	Overall KPI Goals	Y1 KPI Goals	Y1 KPIs Realized	Y2 KPI Goals	Y2 KPIs Realized	Y3 KPI Goals	Y3 KPIs Realized	Total
Conference papers: Published	20	4	15	6	23	10	19	57
Conference papers: International presentations	30	5	16	10	19	15	16	51
Journal articles: Published articles	8	2	1	3	5	6	6	12
Journal Special Issues: Published	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Project workshops: (40 participants) organized	2	0	0	1	0	1	1	2
Tutorials: Scientific ExtremeXP tutorials with UCs	3	0	0	1	0	2	0	0
Tutorials: 6 industrial UC tutorials	6	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Tutorials: 6 industrial training courses (1 Master class)	6	0	0	2	1	2	2	3
Collaboration: 6 EU project collaboration meetings	6	1	2	2	4	3	0	6
Collaboration: 2 scientific UC association memberships	2	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Collaborations: 6 industrial UC associations memberships	6	2	0	2	2	2	0	2
Education: 6 university intervention mentioning the project	6	1	0	2	3	3	2	5
Exhibitions and fairs: 3 ExtremeXP software demonstrations	3	0	0	1	0	5	3	3
Exhibitions and fairs: 6 UC demonstrations	6	0	0	1	2	5	1	3
Open-source software: 5 released open-source software tools	5	0	0	0	0	5	5	5
EC concertation meetings: 6 attended EC concertation meetings + 6 EC concertation meeting presentations	6	1	1	2	0	3	0	1
Standardization bodies: 3 standardization contributions	3	0	0	1	0	2	0	0
Exhibitions and Shows: 6 Usage Demonstrations with the demonstrator	6	0	0	3	0	3	1	1
TV, Radio, newspapers, and magazines: 5 interviews about the ExtremeXP project and benefits for the general public	7	1	0	3	0	3	1	1
Project website: Web site visits	4.5K	1K	0.6K	1.5K	1.3K	2K	2.56K	4,46K
Project website: File downloads	820	120	0	200	174	500	572	746
Push announcements: Regular push announcements through social media	850	150	17	300	86	400	81	184
Regular newsletter: Regular quarterly newsletter of activities of ExtremeXP	27	6	1	9	13	12	7	21
Technical video clips: 3 min high-quality video presentations	20	8	1	10	4	12	11	16
High-quality brochure: technical approach and activities	1000 prints	-	-	-	-	>=1000 prints	400	400

Table 7-1: ExtremeXP evaluation of KPIs

7.2 Evaluation of dissemination and communication activities

7.2.1 Overall Summary

Over the project lifetime, ExtremeXP successfully achieved the vast majority of its communication and dissemination objectives. The project delivered results **of high scientific and technical quality**, ensuring **strong visibility** within academic and European research and innovation communities.

While a limited number of dissemination KPIs were only partially achieved, these deviations were the result of deliberate prioritisation choices, ambitious targets defined at proposal stage, and project maturity constraints. Importantly, they did not affect the overall objectives, scientific relevance, or strategic outcomes of the project.

Overall, WP7 demonstrated **strong performance**, particularly in **scientific dissemination**, **European collaboration**, and **open science practices**, while highlighting areas for improvement related to industrial outreach and public facing communication.

7.2.2 Areas of Partial Achievement

While the majority of dissemination and communication objectives were successfully achieved, a limited number of KPIs were only partially met. These partial achievements do not reflect a lack of activity or commitment, but rather result from a combination of evolving dissemination practices, ambitious targets defined at proposal stage, and project maturity constraints. A qualitative interpretation of these KPIs, supported by selected quantitative references from the monitoring table (Table 7-1), is therefore necessary to provide a balanced assessment of WP7 effectiveness.

Some KPIs related to **printed communication material**, such as “High-quality brochure: technical approach and activities”, were only partially achieved by design. While an overall target of **1000** printed brochures was defined, the achieved number reported in Table 7-1 is **400** copies. Over the project lifetime, the consortium progressively shifted towards digital-first dissemination approaches, prioritising online resources, QR codes, website content, and electronic communication channels. This choice reflects current stakeholder behaviour and sustainability considerations, while still ensuring targeted use of printed material for selected high-value events.

Similarly, the KPI “**Push announcements: Regular push announcements through social media**” was defined with a very ambitious quantitative target of **850** push announcements over the project duration. As reported in Table 7-1, the achieved number amounts to **184** announcements. Reaching the planned target would have required communication actions at an almost daily frequency. In practice, the consortium deliberately favoured relevance, timing, and content quality over volume, ensuring that push announcements were aligned with concrete project milestones, events, and mature outputs rather than pursuing numerical targets alone.

Other KPIs were impacted primarily by project maturity and timing constraints. For instance, the KPI “**Technical video clips: 3 min high-quality video presentations**” defined a target of **20** videos, while **16** videos were effectively produced by the end of the project. Similarly, KPIs related to public and industrial demonstrations, such as “**Exhibitions and Shows: 6 Usage Demonstrations with the demonstrator**”, reached an achieved value of **3** demonstrations out of the **6** initially planned. These activities depend on stable, demonstrable results and sufficient technical readiness, which were reached mainly in the later phases of the project. As a result, dissemination efforts were consciously prioritised towards scientifically mature outputs, including peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, and open-source releases, ensuring credibility and long-term impact.

Overall, these partial achievements concern a limited subset of indicators and reflect conscious prioritisation choices and contextual constraints rather than weaknesses in the dissemination and

communication strategy. They do not undermine the overall effectiveness of WP7, which delivered strong scientific visibility, European-level collaboration, and sustainable dissemination outcomes.

7.2.3 Context and Contributing Factors

The partial achievement of some dissemination and communication KPIs (as detailed in Section 7.2.2) can be explained by the following contextual and organisational factors:

- **Project maturity:** KPIs related to public demonstrations, industrial-oriented actions and technical video production depend on stable and demonstrable results. In ExtremeXP, such maturity was reached mainly in the later phases of the project, limiting the achievable numbers for these KPIs.
- **Industrial stakeholder availability:** Some KPIs involving tutorials, demonstrations and standardisation-oriented dissemination were impacted by the availability and prioritisation constraints of industrial partners.
- **Organisational transition:** the departure of **Activeeon**, initially responsible for communication activities, resulted in a temporary gap of approximately four months before **Interactive 4D (I4D)** resumed and stabilised communication efforts.

These factors mainly affected a limited subset of KPIs (notably videos, demonstrations and selected industrial dissemination actions), while the **overall dissemination and communication strategy remained coherent and effective.**

7.2.4 Lessons Learned

Based on the experience gained during the project, the following lessons can be drawn, particularly in relation to the KPIs that were only partially achieved:

- Dissemination actions requiring mature demonstrators (e.g. public demonstrations, videos, industrial tutorials) benefit from being planned later or phased according to technical readiness.
- Quantitative communication targets (e.g. push announcements) should allow flexibility to prioritise relevance and content quality over volume, while remaining aligned with realistic content production rhythms.
- Resource-intensive dissemination formats such as videos and demonstrations require dedicated planning and buffering to account for dependencies on result maturity and partner availability.

These lessons will inform future Horizon Europe projects and follow-up initiatives, contributing to more realistic KPI definition and impact-driven dissemination planning.

7.2.5 Forward Looking Perspective

Despite some partially achieved KPIs, ExtremeXP delivered **strong scientific, technical, and collaborative impact.** The project established a robust foundation for continued exploitation and dissemination within academic and opensource ecosystems. The experience gained, particularly in managing constraints and reprioritisation, will directly inform and strengthen future communication and dissemination strategies.

Overall, ExtremeXP can be considered a **successful project with mature results, high scientific credibility, and clear pathways for long-term impact.**

8 Sustainability Plan for ExtremeXP

The sustainability of ExtremeXP beyond the project duration relies on the continued visibility, accessibility, and reuse of its scientific and technical outcomes. Although the Horizon Europe funding

ends at M36 (+ 2-month extension), the consortium has established solid foundations to ensure that the project's results remain accessible, visible, and impactful within the scientific, industrial, and innovation ecosystems.

Sustainability is primarily ensured through:

- the continued dissemination of results via scientific and professional events,
- long-term visibility through high-quality scientific publications,
- and the preservation of open-source software, communication assets, and collaboration networks developed during the project.

This approach ensures that ExtremeXP outcomes can continue to be referenced, reused, and built upon by external stakeholders after the end of the project.

8.1 Indicative Dissemination Events

After the project completion, ExtremeXP results are expected to continue to be disseminated through relevant scientific and industrial events, building on the strong presence already established during the project lifetime. Indicative dissemination channels include:

- Major European and international conferences in data analytics, artificial intelligence, and big data (e.g. EDBT, VLDB, ICDE, Big Data from Space, EBDVF),
- Thematic workshops and symposia related to AI, data spaces, explainable AI, and extreme data,
- Community and cluster-driven events organized within European initiatives such as EUDATA+, AI.BIG, and related data and AI ecosystems.

Participation in such events will allow the ExtremeXP results to remain visible to academic, industrial, and institutional audiences, fostering continued knowledge exchange and networking opportunities beyond the funded project period.

8.2 Indicative Scientific Journals and Magazines

The scientific sustainability of ExtremeXP is further supported through long-term visibility in established peer-reviewed journals and scientific publication venues. Results produced during the project are expected to continue to be referenced, extended, and reused within the scientific community.

Indicative publication venues aligned with ExtremeXP research themes include:

- Journals and proceedings in data management, artificial intelligence, and software systems (e.g. Information Systems, VLDB Journal, TKDE, Journal of Intelligent Information Systems),
- AI- and data-oriented conference proceedings and book series (Springer, IEEE, ACM),
- Open-access repositories and platforms ensuring long-term availability of publications.

By relying on recognized scientific journals and open-access dissemination channels, ExtremeXP ensures that its research contributions remain accessible, citable, and reusable beyond the project's lifetime.

9 Response to Reviewers' Recommendations (Dissemination & Exploitation)

This section summarizes how the ExtremeXP consortium has addressed the reviewers' recommendations related to dissemination, communication, and early exploitation actions.

Reviewer Recommendation	Actions Implemented	Evidence (Website)
Zenodo & Open-Source Datasets	ExtremeXP produced and released open-source datasets derived from experiments carried out in the five use	https://extremexp.eu , menu Resources (sub-menu Deliverables)

	cases, using Zenodo to disseminate experimental results and related research artefacts for community reuse. These datasets describe experiments, workflows, input, output data and results (e.g. metrics).	
Improve message formulation & tagging	Communication messages were refined to highlight key innovations and benefits, using concise formats, appropriate hashtags, and best practices adapted to limited user attention spans across social media, newsletters, and the project website.	LinkedIn https://extremexp.eu/events/
Fix publications list	The publications section of the website was consolidated and aligned with the authoritative list presented in this deliverable, improving usability and completeness.	https://extremexp.eu/publications/
Describe all use cases	All project use cases were clearly described and published online, providing a comprehensive and accessible overview of ExtremeXP application domains and results.	https://extremexp.eu/category/use-cases/
Single access point for software & data	A centralized section on the project portal was established to group all links to software repositories and datasets, with clear descriptions and explanations to support discoverability and reuse.	https://extremexp.eu , menu Resources (sub-menu Software)
Early exploitation & adoption	Early engagement actions (demonstrations, workshops, presentations) involved industrial and research stakeholders, providing feedback that informed iterative improvements and supported early uptake of project results.	https://extremexp.eu/events/

Table 9-1: Response to Reviewers' Recommendations

10 Conclusions

The communication and dissemination activities carried out within ExtremeXP have effectively supported the visibility, credibility, and impact of the project throughout its duration. Through a coherent strategy and sustained collective effort, the consortium ensured wide dissemination of its scientific and technical results across European and international research and innovation communities.

ExtremeXP achieved particularly strong results in scientific dissemination, with a high volume of peer-reviewed publications and conference contributions, as well as active participation in major European events and clustering initiatives. These actions reinforced the project's positioning within the data and AI ecosystem and facilitated knowledge exchange with related initiatives.

The combination of scientific excellence, open-source dissemination, digital communication channels, and European-level collaboration has established solid foundations for the long-term visibility and reuse of ExtremeXP outcomes beyond the end of Horizon Europe funding.

Communication assets, publications, software artefacts, and collaboration networks developed during the project will remain accessible and valuable to the wider community.

Overall, ExtremeXP successfully delivered its communication and dissemination objectives in line with the project's scope and maturity, ensuring sustainable impact and alignment with European research and innovation priorities.

Appendix: Promotion Event Templates

The following appendix contains further examples of event templates that have been completed by other project partners. These examples collectively showcase the range of activities undertaken and support the ongoing communication efforts of the project.

Event Name	BiDS 2023	Event Organizer	SatCen, ESA and JRC
Location	Vienna, Austria	Start date / End date	6-9 November 2023
Link to the event	https://www.bigdatafromspace2023.org		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
LE CARVENNEC Arnaud	CS GROUP	Speaker (poster presenter)
Rationale for Participation: <i>Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?</i>		
The opportunity to present ExtremeXP use case at a large conference bringing key players from industry, academia, EU entities, and governments together. A unique opportunity to discuss the latest innovations, as well as the practical challenges encountered in the context of big data in space.		
LinkedIn Post		
<i>The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.</i>		
ExtremeXP partner CS GROUP attended the Big Data from Space 2023 (BiDS) event held in Vienna, Austria, from 6-9 November. During the conference, they presented their work on “Improving Flash Flood Forecasting through the Use of AI”. This provided an excellent opportunity to showcase the ExtremeXP project to potential end-users and engage with stakeholders from the industry, academia, EU entities, and government.		
Corporate presentation of the event		
<i>Report here the official presentation of the event</i>		
Big Data from Space 2023 (BiDS) brings together key actors from industry, academia, EU entities and government to reveal user needs, exchange ideas and showcase latest technical solutions and applications touching all aspects of space and big data technologies. BiDS provides a premier opportunity for practitioners, researchers, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, as well as practical challenges encountered in the context of big data from space.		
Illustration of the event (logo/picture)		
<i>Report here the official illustration of the event</i>		
Pictures in the folder		

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS

Event Name	Hydrospace 2023	Event Organizer	ESA and CNES
Location	Lisbon, Portugal	Start date / End date	27 November to 1 December 2023
Link to the event	https://www.hydrospace2023.org/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
LARNIER Kevin	CS GROUP	Speaker (poster presenter)
SAVINAUD Mickael	CS GROUP	Speaker (poster presenter)
Rationale for Participation: <i>Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?</i>		
<p>The opportunity to present ExtremeXP use case at a major workshop bringing together key players from EO scientists, water researchers and students, modelers, Earth system and climate scientists, industry, operational agencies, policy makers, representatives of local communities and other stakeholders interested in sharing their knowledge and experience and in contributing to drive the scientific agenda for advancing EO water research and future applications.</p>		
LinkedIn Post		
<p><i>The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.</i></p>		
<p>ExtremeXP partner CS GROUP attended the fifth Space for Hydrology Workshop which took place in Lisbon from Monday 27 November to Friday 1 December 2023. During the workshop, they presented their work on “Improving Flash Flood Forecasting through the Use of AI”. This provided an excellent opportunity to showcase the ExtremeXP project and their latest developments and work in EO for water research and hydrology to potential end-users and engage with stakeholders from the industry, academia, EU entities, and government.</p>		
Corporate presentation of the event		
<p><i>Report here the official presentation of the event</i></p>		
<p>HYDROSPACE 2023 aims at reviewing the latest advances in the use of Earth Observation (EO) technology for water cycle science, hydrology and its applications, exploring the potential offered by the existing and coming EO satellites together with advanced modelling and novel technologies as well as the main challenges and opportunities to enhance our current capacity to observe, understand and predict the water cycle, and its impacts and feedbacks with human activities and ecosystems.</p>		
Illustration of the event (logo/picture)		
<p><i>Report here the official illustration of the event</i></p>		
Picture in the folder		

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)
COMMENTS

Event Name	Future Intelligence 2023	Event Organizer	Aerospace Valley, AD'OCC ANITI Toulouse
Location	Toulouse, France	Start date / End date	November 7, 2023
Link to the event	https://futureintelligence.tech/edition-7-nov-2023/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
SAVINAUD Mickael	CS GROUP	Speaker
GAUDDISART Vincent	CS GROUP	Participant

Rationale for Participation: <i>Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?</i>
The opportunity to present ExtremeXP use case at a large AI community and promotes the work of the project.
LinkedIn Post
<i>The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.</i>
CS GROUP, a sponsor of Future Intelligence held in Toulouse on November 7, had the opportunity to present their activities and AI tools at the event. Mickaël Savinaud, Head of the CS GROUP Image Processing Skills Center, had the opportunity to highlight the ExtremeXP use case project, focused on 'Improving Flash Flood Forecasting through the Use of AI'. The occasion provided an excellent opportunity to showcase the ExtremeXP project to AI experts and engage in discussions about the opportunities and challenges associated with the utilization of AI in the space sector.
Corporate presentation of the event
<i>Report here the official presentation of the event</i>
FUTURE INTELLIGENCE is a day organized around AI, an opportunity to meet the AI community: experts, innovators, legislators and all the professionals involved at every level of the AI value chain, from creation to optimization - artificial intelligence experts.
Illustration of the event (logo/picture)
<i>Report here the official illustration of the event</i>
Picture in the folder

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS

Event Name	IEEE IGARSS 2024	Event Organizer	ESA
Location	Athena, Greece	Start date / End date	7-12 July 2024
Link to the event	https://www.2024.ieeeigarss.org/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Gwendoline STEPHAN	CS	Speaker
Rationale for Participation: <i>Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?</i>		
Presentation of the hydrological model which is the tool used to generate data for the UC about flash floods.		
LinkedIn Post		

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity-7221177003255705600-ttRf?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACjvgUUBvq0HTtQi0sVM3hfxoeT92V0H1Mo

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

On behalf of the IGARSS 2024 Organizing Committee we are delighted to invite you to Athens, Greece, for the 44th annual “International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium - IGARSS 2024” of the IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society, the world's largest technical professional organization.

The Conference, which for the first time in history will be hosted in Greece, will take place on the 7th until 12th of July 2024, at the Megaron Athens International Conference Center.

It is the leading meeting of more than 2.500 esteemed scientists and professionals in the Remote Sensing field worldwide. It distinctively contributes to the exchange of views, sharing of experiences and the training of younger scientists, opening new perspectives for research development and investments in the sector.

Under this year’s theme “Acting for Sustainability and Resilience”, we anticipate stimulating enlightening debates for opening science and innovation, towards the creation of innovative solutions for the benefit of societies.

The Scientific Program of this IGARSS, emphasizes on sustainable development in accordance with the goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda, including scientific publications, lectures, presentations and intriguing forums, specializing in Remote Sensing. Delegates will have the opportunity to get involved with the latest scientific achievements of the Greek centers of research, education, and business development. Scientists, representatives of the industrial sector and start-up companies, as well as students from all over the world are invited to delve into the latest research and technological advancements in the field of space and its applications.

IGARSS 2024 will be hosted by the National Observatory of Athens - Operational Unit “BEYOND Centre of Earth Observation Research and Satellite Remote Sensing” of Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing, with the support of the National Technical University of Athens and the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas.

Athens, one of the world’s oldest cities, the birthplace of democracy, arts, science, and philosophy of western civilization is waiting for you, for an exciting journey through time. Under the shadow of Parthenon, Athens reflects its enlightening history and culture combined with the perfect Mediterranean climate and the legendary Greek sunlight. An exciting mix of glorious culture with an astonishing natural urban beauty will keep you mesmerized.

“Enlightened science reflected from the Acropolis of Athens” is our motivation and we look forward to welcoming you all, for a memorable IGARSS 2024, where we will join forces to develop resilient solutions ensuring a sustainable and inclusive future for all in a world of continuous and overlapping disruption.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

SAVE THE DATE

**IEEE
IGARSS
2024** | July 7-12
ATHENS
GREECE

International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium

Acting for Sustainability and Resilience

Supported by

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS			
Event Name	EUROPEAN BIG DATA VALUE FORUM	Event Organizer	BDVA
Location	Budapest, Hungary	Start date / End date	2-4 October 2024
Link to the event	https://bdva.eu/events/european-big-data-value-forum-ebdvf-2024/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Pauline Delporte	CS	Speaker
Rationale for Participation: <i>Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?</i>		
EBDVF was the occasion to present the project and 2 uses cases. ExtremeXP deals with big data. The variety and the quantity are managed by the framework. In that way, it was interesting to present the breakthroughs made by the teams of the project.		
LinkedIn Post		
<i>The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.</i>		
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity-7244064366172467201-6257?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACjvgUUBvq0HTtQi0sVM3hfxoeT92V0H1Mo		
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/extremexp_extremexp-ebdvf2024-innovation-activity-7248990940000923648-jCSJ?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACjvgUUBvq0HTtQi0sVM3hfxoeT92V0H1Mo		
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/extremexp_extremexp-floodprediction-ai-activity-7247920312548257793-ENWS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACjvgUUBvq0HTtQi0sVM3hfxoeT92V0H1Mo		
Corporate presentation of the event		
<i>Report here the official presentation of the event</i>		
<p>BDVA is glad to announce the opening of registration for the European Big Data Value Forum 2024! The European Big Data Value Forum is BDVA's flagship event, bringing the whole European data-driven AI research and innovation community together to share knowledge, collaborate and celebrate achievements. This year's event will take place from 2-4 October 2024 in Budapest, Hungary. EBDVF 2024 is organised in collaboration with local partners: AI & Aut Expo, Eötvös Loránd University, Idealist ICT, Neumann Technology Platform and HUN-REN SZTAKI (Institute for Computer Science and Control).</p> <p>EBDVF event brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policymakers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI. The programme includes the most important topics of the community, presented by our members, collaboration partners and representatives from European research and innovation projects. Together we are delivering</p>		

sessions and workshops shaping the way forward for big data and data spaces, illuminating how businesses can harness the power of Trustworthy AI and discuss the role of high-performance computing as an enabler for digital transformation. We take a comprehensive view of these topics from the perspective of many European economic sectors not forgetting the societal implications of the rapidly advancing technologies

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS

Event Name	Short Course/Tutorial on Big Data Analytics for Natural Disaster Management	Event Organizer	Icarus
Location	Online	Start date / End date	3 December 2024
Link to the event	https://icarus.csd.auth.gr/short-course-on-big-data-analytics-for-natural-disaster-management/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Pauline Delporte	CS	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

The UC headed by CS Group is dealing with the flash flood prediction. It is currently one of disasters that causes the most damage economically and humanely. In this short course, we presented our work how big data and IA can help to manage this kind of crisis.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

This short course on Big Data Analytics for Natural Disaster Management (NDM) provides a comprehensive overview and in-depth presentation of advanced technologies involved in the acquisition and analysis of Big Data for NDM. NDM can be greatly improved by developing automated means for precise semantic mapping and phenomenon evolution predictions in real-time. Several extreme data sources can significantly help towards achieving this goal: a) autonomous devices and smart sensors at the edge, equipped with AI-capabilities; b) satellite images; c) topographical data; d) official meteorological data, predictions or warnings published in the Web; and e) geosocial media data (including text, image and video). Such heterogeneous data sources provide a prime extreme data example: a) they are diverse; b) voluminous; c) fast and frequently updated; d) complex; e) multilingual; f) have very disperse sources (satellite, drone, sensors, social media, maps); and h) have extreme values.

The course consists of ten lectures, covering important topics and presenting state-of-the-art technologies in: a) Big Data acquisition using sensors, drones, satellites, the Web and social media platforms; b) Big Data analysis based on Deep Learning; c) accurate phenomena modelling; and d) analysis, forecasting and risk management for improved NDM. The presented technologies find practical application in developing an advanced NDM support system that dynamically exploits multiple data sources and AI technologies for providing an accurate assessment of an evolving crisis situation.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

Students, scientists, engineer

COMMENTS

Event Name	Living Planet Symposium	Event Organizer	ESA
Location	Budapest, Hungary	Start date / End date	23-27 Juin 2025
Link to the event	https://lps25.esa.int/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Pauline Delporte	CS	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

LPS is a conference on Earth Observation. It was the occasion to present our work about the prediction of fast floods in a session called Spaceborne data for the analysis of Natural Hazards and AI: new insights from Artificial Intelligence technologies and recent missions

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ugcPost-7345440997260095489-_Mal?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACjvgUUBvq0HTtQi0sVM3hfxoeT92V0H1Mo

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

Held every three years, ESA's Living Planet Symposia are among the world's premier events on Earth observation. The symposia continue to expand in both size and scope. With the climate crisis intensifying, the Living Planet Symposium 2025 (LPS25) emphasises transitioning from 'observation to climate action and sustainability for Earth'.

The event provides a forum to present and discuss the latest scientific findings and applications based on satellite data, and to review the contribution that data and technologies have made and could further make in addressing environmental and societal challenges. The symposium will showcase innovative products, services, missions and initiatives, with the overarching goal of demonstrating how science, society, policymaking, businesses and the economy can all benefit from observations made from space.

During the five-day event, diverse communities united by a common interest in exploiting Earth observation data will gather together, creating a unique opportunity to meet and network with space enthusiasts from a wide range of sectors.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)
Scientists, students, engineers
COMMENTS

Event Name	Big Data from Space (BiDS) 2025	Event Organizer	ESA
Location	Riga, Latvia	Start date / End date	29 September – 3 rd October 2025
Link to the event	https://www.bigdatafromspace2025.org/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Gwendoline STEPHAN	CS	Speaker (Poster)

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

The framework ExtremeXP host the CS Group UC. It is helping to manage a big numerous of data coming from multiple sensors. This challenge will be presented in a poster session during this conference.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

The Big Data from Space 2025 (BiDS) event convenes key stakeholders from industry, academia, EU institutions, and governmental entities to explore the evolving landscape of space, big data, and related emerging technologies. It serves as a platform to share user needs, showcase the latest technical solutions and applications, and define future development roadmaps. The conference fosters exchange, discussions on cutting-edge research, practical challenges, and transformative innovations to enhance user experience related to Big Data from Space.

Together, we want to explore and learn how space- driven insights and foresight, and synergies between diverse space domains and technologies - Earth Observation, Space Science, Weather, Climate and Planetary Observation, Navigation, Positioning and Telecommunications, Mission Operations and System Engineering - can provide a robust foundation for evidence-informed decision-making. These insights are critical in addressing global societal challenges, including climate change, sustainable competitiveness, and civil security.

Key objectives of BiDS 2025 include:

- Showcasing and investigating the impact of Big Data from Space on society’s grand challenges, such as climate change, as well as key policies at the European and global levels, including the European Green Deal and the UN 2030 Sustainable Development Goals.
- Identifying breakthrough data science technologies that accelerate space-based Big Data insight and foresight, transitioning from research and innovation to operational applications.

- Promoting open science and innovation, interoperability of solutions, and cross-disciplinary collaboration, building on open and FAIR data principles, digital trust, cloud-based technologies, and Data Spaces.
- Discussing the future of space data and technology, identifying next gamechangers, technological advancements, and establishing an innovation roadmap to maximize the benefits of space-derived data and technologies.

The 2025 edition of BiDS will not only focus on the technologies enabling insight and foresight from Big Data but explore how Big Data from Space-driven innovation can enhance competitiveness, support evidence-informed policy, and benefit society and the economy. Today, the accessibility of global, free, and open space and geospatial data is expanding through EU initiatives such as the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, Destination Earth (DestinE), the Common European Data Spaces, and the AI Factories, or ESA's Digital Twin Earth program. Additionally, advancements in Deep Tech, including quantum computing, neuromorphic sensing, and connected computing in space, are paving the way for new disruptive applications. These developments will drive additional value and impact across research, business, and policy domains.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS			
Event Name	EUROPEAN BIG DATA VALUE FORUM	Event Organizer	BDVA
Location	DGI BYEN, COPENHAGEN, DENMARK	Start date / End date	12 - 14 November 2025
Link to the event	https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/2025-edition/programme/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Pauline Delporte & Yasmine BOULFANI	CS	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

EBDVF was the occasion to present the project and uses cases. ExtremeXP deals with big data. The variety and the quantity are managed by the framework. In that way, it was interesting to present the breakthroughs made by the teams of the project.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/csgroup-space_horizoneu-ebdvf25-extremexp-activity-7389911952896208896-KzNp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAKWmTIBWrryKjIEEOU-UcNhoOQPqsG BK8

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity-7394336892877656064-GJta?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAKWmTIBWrryKjIEEOU-UcNhoOQPqsG BK8

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity-7394700486563540992-whso?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAAKWmTIBWrryKjIEEOU-UcNhoOQPqsG BK8

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

CS GROUP participated in the European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2025 in Copenhagen, organized by the BDVA - Big Data Value Association. As a partner in the ExtremeXP project, CS GROUP contributed to a joint exhibition stand with the EUDATA+ cluster, of which ExtremeXP is a member. Yasmine Boulfani and Pauline Delporte represented the company at the event.

During a session organised by the EUDATA+ cluster, Pauline Delporte presented the principal research on AI-based flash flood forecasting—a significant advancement realized within the ExtremeXP project.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

GROUP OF PROJECTS

EUROPEAN
**BIG DATA
VALUE** FORUM

12-14 NOV | COPENHAGEN - DENMARK

EUDATA+

IN COLLABORATION WITH

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

Co-funded by
the European Union

COMMENTS			
Event Name	EEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks	Event Organizer	IEEE
Location	Dresden	Start date / End date	7->9/11/2023
Link to the event	https://nfvsdn2023.ieee-nfvsdn.org/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Sonu Preetam	i2CAT	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

Presentation of scientific paper on research topics aligned with the Cybersecurity use-case

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

N/A

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

The **9th IEEE Conference on Network Functions Virtualization and Software-Defined Networking (IEEE NFV-SDN 2023)** will be an in-person event in 2023. The conference will be from 7-9 November 2023 in Dresden, Germany.

In 2023, IEEE NFV-SDN conference will focus on the foundation, design, verification, operation, security, and evolution of virtualized network functions, with the current emphasis on Cloud Native CNFs in addition to the more traditional VNFs. Additionally of interest includes advances in SDN concepts. Performance, manageability and more recently the implications of energy consumption continue to be active areas as well as the virtualization efforts going on in the radio and the management of the radio using AI/ML.

In addition, the 2023 conference includes the investigation of the relationship Beyond 5G/6G networks and transmission technologies will have with applications within the NFV architectural concepts. Special interest will be given to how Beyond 5G/6G applications are designed, orchestrated, and managed by NFV mechanisms and VNFs. IEEE NFV-SDN 2023 continues as the premier IEEE event on the latest NFV and SDN concepts and mechanisms.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

Mainly academic, with a predominance of PhD student. No quantitative information available.

COMMENTS

- Paper name An Approach for Intelligent Behaviour-Based Threat Modelling with Explanations (**Sonu Preetam**), presented in the doctoral symposium, session PHD1: Intelligent network.

Event Name	GÉANT Security Days 2024	Event Organizer	GÉANT Consortium
Location	Prague, Czechia	Start date / End date	27->29/05/25
Link to the event	https://security.geant.org/geant-security-days-2024/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Sonu Preetam	i2CAT	Speaker
Xavier Marrugat	i2CAT	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

Presentation of the cybersecurity use-case to an audience targeted for exploitation.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

N/A

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

April 2024 brings the first edition of GÉANT Security Days. This gives an opportunity to bring together security practitioners from across research and education, including NRENs, universities, colleges, research infrastructures, and other areas with an interest in security. We invite you to join us in Prague, and to submit your contributions, ideas, questions and challenges to the research and education community. The theme for this meeting will be: Securing Tomorrow's Knowledge, addressing the following main areas:

Cybersecurity in Academia: Explore specific challenges and solutions related to cybersecurity for universities and research centres.

Emerging Threats: Address new and emerging threats to research and education, such as ransomware, phishing, and IoT vulnerabilities.

Incident Response and Recovery: Highlight strategies and practices for responding to security incidents and recovering from them effectively.

Collaborative Initiatives: Encourage collaboration between research and educational institutions to enhance security efforts, share threat intelligence, and collaborate on awareness and training initiatives.

Ethics and Security: Ensure the services and approaches we use are ethical, designed to support users, and meet societal goals such as green security initiatives.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

No information

COMMENTS

Detail about the presentation: <https://events.geant.org/event/1515/contributions/1694/> (with ExtremeXP Acknowledgement)

Event Name	Webtech “Comments on reliable and precise decisions from what?”	Event Organizer	Aktantis
Location	Zaragoza, Spain	Start date / End date	19/09/2025
Link to the event	https://www.aktantis.com/2025/07/02/webtech-comment-prendre-des-decisions-fiables-et-precises-a-partir-de-donnees/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Maxime Compastie	I2CAT Foundation	Speaker
Iyad Alshabani	BitSparkles	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

Presentation of the project objectives, outcome & cybersecurity use-cases

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

- <https://x.com/i2CAT/status/1968556048790261952>
- <https://bsky.app/profile/i2cat.net/post/3lz3ogvoh7o22>
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aktantis_webtech-activity-7370846922477182976-04YO

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

Data-driven decisions can be vital and have a phenomenal impact on the environment, society, and businesses.

Many critical areas such as cybersecurity, crisis management, predictive maintenance, mobility, and public safety are increasingly disrupted by these new ways of leveraging the proliferation of data for effective decision-making.

However, producing data-driven insights that can be used and trusted by decision-makers is far from easy.

At this WebTech, discover ExtremeXP (<https://extremexp.eu/>), a new paradigm that relies on experimentation-driven analysis to deliver accurate, fit-for-purpose, and reliable data-driven insights by evaluating different variants of complex analyses, taking into account end-user preferences and feedback in an automated manner.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

#WEBTECH

COMMENT PRENDRE DES DECISIONS FIABLES ET PRECISES A PARTIR DE DONNEES ?

AKTANTIS

19/09/20
11h00 à 12h

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

25 members in the (online) audience

COMMENTS

Event Name	DATA WEEK 2025	Event Organizer	Big Data Value Association (BDVA)
Location	ATHENS, GREECE	Start date / End date	27-28/05/2025
Link to the event	https://data-week.eu/2025-edition/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Gregoris Mentzas, Dimitris Apostolou, Yiannis Verginadis	ICCS	Speakers
George Papastefanatos	ARC	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

As part of the EUDATA+ cluster of projects Yiannis Verginadis was invited as a speaker and panellist in the session: Solutions for Data Trading and Pricing. This was a forward-looking session on new models for data commercialization and the development of a Single Digital Market through Data

Spaces. Assist. Prof. Yiannis Verginadis provided insights into our contribution to experimentation orchestration, decentralized data management, and NFT-based provenance in AI workflows.

As part of DataNexus cluster George Papastefanatos was invited as a speaker in the session: Extreme data driven solutions and services – Updated perspectives and Challenges for Europe. This was a showcase of five projects from the DataNexus cluster and one from AI.BIG, highlighting how extreme data challenges are being tackled across domains. George Papastefanatos, as the coordinator of ExtremeXP, presented the milestones and accomplishments of the project.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

Over the past two days, we had the pleasure of attending [hashtag#DataWeek2025](#), representing [IMU/ICCS, Information Management Unit, National Technical University of Athens](#) at one of Europe's key gatherings for the [#Data](#) and [#AI](#) innovation ecosystem — co-organized this year in Athens, Greece at [OTEAcademy!](#)

The event brought together leading researchers, industry experts, and policymakers to explore cutting-edge technologies, emerging initiatives, and the open challenges at the intersection of data, trust, and artificial intelligence. From insightful sessions to interactive workshops and meaningful networking opportunities, the experience was very enriching!

Some highlights that stood out:

- "Sisyphus' Code: The Ongoing Quest for Trustworthy AI" – An eye-opening session where experts from across Europe examined the complex journey toward responsible, human-centred AI. Discussions focused on trust, transparency, and collaborative governance as foundations for AI that serves society. Professor [Gregoris Mentzas](#) moderated this session and [Dimitris Apostolou](#) presented key results from EU projects on AI trustworthiness, namely THEMIS 5.0 and FAITH.
- "DataNexus: Extreme data driven solutions and services – Updated perspectives and Challenges for Europe" – A showcase of five projects from the DataNexus cluster and one from AI.BIG, highlighting how extreme data challenges are being tackled across domains. It was great to see [George Papastefanatos](#), the coordinator of [ExtremeXP](#), present the milestones and accomplishments of the project.

- “EUDATA+: Solutions for Data Trading and Pricing” – A forward-looking session that brought together industry and research to discuss new models for data commercialization and the development of a Single Digital Market through Data Spaces. Special kudos to [Yiannis Verginadis](#) from our team, who provided insights into our contribution to experimentation orchestration, decentralized data management, and NFT-based provenance in AI workflows.
- [#DataWeek2025](#) was a strong reminder that collaboration and responsible innovation are key to unlocking data’s full value and advancing Europe’s digital future.

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

Data Week is the spring gathering of the Data and AI research and innovation community. In Data Week, the participants share knowledge and results, discuss topics of common interest, find synergies, build new collaborations, and identify new challenges and recommendations. Data Week also links the communities and their results to the European policies and market needs and brings European initiatives and activities closer to local communities.

Organised by BDVA, Data Week 2025 centers its focus on the fundamental elements of Data Value creation. Artificial intelligence (AI) serves as a pivotal tool in unlocking data value through various means. Creating value from data also requires viewing it from an ecosystem perspective and fostering collaboration among multiple stakeholders, which lays the groundwork needed for research excellence, that is required to be rapidly put into action for competitiveness and societal benefit.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

The audience included a diverse crowd, from academia to industry, with a special emphasis on the latter bringing together researchers, policy makers, industry experts, and practitioners with an interest on all the fundamental elements of data value creation.

COMMENTS

Event Name	37th International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI 2025)	Event Organizer	
Location	ATHENS, GREECE	Start date / End date	03-05/11/2025
Link to the event	https://easyconferences.eu/ictai2025/program/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Georgia Gkioka	ICCS	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

The event focused on tools with Artificial Intelligence and ExtremeXP partner (ICCS) presented our work regarding Experiment Cards, a lightweight AI documentation and knowledge management framework designed to capture the dynamic experimentation process.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

ICCS participated in the 37th IEEE International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence ([#ICTAI2025](#))!

Georgia Gkioka had the pleasure of presenting joint work with [Dimitris Apostolou](#), [Yiannis Verginadis](#), and Prof. [Gregoris Mentzas](#):

Experiment Cards: A Documentation Framework for Trustworthy AI Experiments
Our work introduces Experiment Cards, a lightweight framework that captures the dynamic nature of AI experimentation, combining human-in-the-loop documentation with automated metadata extraction to enhance transparency and reproducibility in AI knowledge management.

The conference was full of inspiring discussions and research presentations — from advances of Deep Learning to the growing role of LLMs and responsible AI. This research was conducted in the context of the EU project [ExtremeXP](#) within [IMU/ICCS, Information Management Unit, National Technical University of Athens](#) of [ICCS - NTUA](#)

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

The IEEE International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI) has been a leading IEEECS annual scientific meeting for three decades. It provides a major international forum where the creation and exchange of ideas related to artificial intelligence are fostered among academia, industry, and government agencies. The conference facilitates the cross-fertilization of these ideas and promotes their transfer into practical tools, for developing intelligent systems and pursuing artificial intelligence applications. ICTAI encompasses all technical aspects of specifying, developing, and evaluating the theoretical underpinnings and applied mechanisms of the AI-based components of computer tools such as algorithms, architectures, and languages.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

The session in which the presentation about the experiment cards took place included a diverse crowd, from academia to industry, with an interest in practical applications of AI.

COMMENTS

Event Name	16 th Conference on ENTERprise Information Systems (CENTERIS 2024)	Event Organizer	Association for Information Systems (AIS)
Location	Funchal, Madeira, Portugal	Start date / End date	13-15/11/2024
Link to the event	https://centeris.scika.org/?page=home		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Yiannis Verginadis	ICCS	Speaker

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

The event focused on Enterprise Information Systems and is organized by the Association for Information Systems (AIS). ExtremeXP partner (ICCS) presented our work regarding the NFT-based Data Provenance mechanisms, a novel framework able to integrate, in a transparent manner, quality-related metadata on datasets used for training the AI-enabled emerging technologies in the field of EIS systems. These metadata are minted as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) over the blockchain.

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

No LinkedIn post available

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

CENTERIS, Enterprise Information Systems are addressed comprehensively from the technological, organizational, and social perspectives, aiming at presenting, discussing, and disseminating current developments, case studies, new integrated approaches and practical solutions and applications.

Overall objectives of the conference:

- To discuss the importance of Enterprise Information Systems and the emerging technological developments (information integration, enterprise integration, functionalities);
- To introduce the state-of-the-art solutions and supported features;
- To present and discuss practical solutions;
- To discuss the open-source movement: opportunities, trends, risks, advantages, and disadvantages;
- To discuss integrated solutions;
- To introduce and discuss the challenges or difficulties associated with the social, organizational, and technological perspectives;
- To discuss organizational and social implications;
- To discuss motivations, problems, and critical success factors on the adoption of Enterprise Information Systems;
- To discuss management issues and challenges;
- To discuss the future trends of Enterprise Information Systems.

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

CENTERIS

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

The conference is targeted to an academic audience (teachers, researchers, and students, mainly from post-graduate studies), IT professionals and managers.

COMMENTS

EVENT PROMOTION

ExtremeXP

Event Name	ExtremeXP Summer School	Event Organizer	FRI, UL
Location	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Start date / End date	22–26 September 2025
Link to the event	https://datatrust.fri.uni-lj.si/summer-school/		

Name	Company	Role (Speaker/participant)
Vlado Stankovski	FRI, UL	Speaker
Atiyeh Ghane	FRI, UL	Participant
Petar Kochovski	FRI, UL	Participant

Rationale for Participation: *Why this event is relevant to ExtremeXP?*

Human-AI Summer School & Doctoral Symposium (22–26 September 2025, Ljubljana), organized by the University of Ljubljana’s Faculty of Computer and Information Science in collaboration with ExtremeXP, brings together cutting-edge themes in human–AI interaction, digital trust, decision-making frameworks, and blockchain for trusted data ecosystems [X \(formerly Twitter\)+1Blockchain for Trusted Data Ecosystems+3FRI+3Blockchain for Trusted Data Ecosystems+3](#).

ExtremeXP partners will lead hands-on workshops on **AI scientific workflows, visualization and decision-simulations** [FRI+4Blockchain for Trusted Data Ecosystems+4Blockchain for Trusted Data Ecosystems+4](#).

LinkedIn Post

The LinkedIn post should introduce the event (name of the event, organiser, date, location, topic), the participants (ExtremeXP partners), and the links to ExtremeXP projects.

 Registration is open!

Join us in Ljubljana this September for the AI Summer School 2025 – a deep dive into Human-AI Interaction, Digital Trust, and Responsible AI.

- When: 22–26 September 2025
- Where: University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- More info & registration: <https://lnkd.in/d8KBWbKG>

- What to expect:
- Keynotes from leading AI researchers
 - Hands-on workshops and interactive sessions
 - Doctoral symposium and networking with fellow PhD students
 - Topics spanning AI ethics, transparency, and real-world impact

 Whether you’re a PhD student, researcher, or practitioner working in AI and digital trust—this is the place to be!

EVENT PROMOTION

ExtremeXP

🔒 Secure your spot before the cut-off dates!

👉 July 10 | August 10

Corporate presentation of the event

Report here the official presentation of the event

Human-AI Summer School & Doctoral Symposium 2025

The Faculty of Computer and Information Science, University of Ljubljana, is proud to host the **Human-AI Summer School & Doctoral Symposium**, taking place from **22–26 September 2025 in Ljubljana, Slovenia**. This international event will bring together leading researchers, industry experts, and doctoral candidates to explore the latest developments in **Human-AI interaction, trusted data ecosystems, decision-making frameworks, digital trust, and blockchain technologies**.

The program will feature **keynote lectures, interactive workshops, and a doctoral symposium**, creating a vibrant space for knowledge exchange, networking, and collaboration. Particular emphasis will be placed on the **ExtremeXP project**, whose partners will contribute hands-on sessions on AI scientific workflows, visualization techniques, and decision-support simulations.

By fostering dialogue between academia, industry, and policymakers, the Summer School aims to strengthen Europe’s capacity in **human-centered and trustworthy AI**, while supporting young researchers in advancing their skills and research impact.

For more details and the full agenda, please visit the official event page:

👉 <https://datatrust.fri.uni-lj.si/summer-school/>

Illustration of the event (logo/picture)

Report here the official illustration of the event

Audience (if presentation done by ExtremeXP partner)

COMMENTS

